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**CLIMATE CHANGE AND CULTURAL HERITAGE: A QUALITATIVE STUDY OF
THE PAETE WOOD CARVERS IN THE PHILIPPINES**

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04 November 2024

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- II. Due acknowledgment has been made in the text to all other material used
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Ma. Jamela V. Dimapilis

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Abstract

The Paete woodcarving community, renowned for its cultural heritage, confronts climate change challenges that threaten their environment-dependent craft. This qualitative study focused into the knowledge, perceptions, experiences, and strategies of Paete's carvers, aiming to comprehend how they navigate climate change's impact on their cultural heritage. Findings reveal a diminishing wood supply, particularly the native tree Batikuling (*Litsea leytensis Merr.*), is exacerbated by climatic variations and deforestation from forest fires. The logging ban policy, implemented to protect forests and mitigate climate change has unintentionally affected woodcarvers due to stringent documentation required for the lawful felling of trees. Furthermore, environmental changes such as extreme weather conditions influenced by climate change also affect woodcarving process. As the wood becomes scarcer, escalating material costs have impacted the livelihoods and economic sustainability of these artisans. Reduced sales during the pandemic disrupted markets and lowered demand for woodcarvings. Despite adversity, the community demonstrates resilience through innovative adaptations and exploration of new mediums for carving. Notably, collaborative efforts between the community and local government such as Batikuling seed propagation, museum curation, educational partnerships, festival carving competitions, and integration of carving in vocational training reflect a shared commitment to sustain Paete's rich cultural heritage in woodcarving and preserve this art form for future generations. As today's artisans grapple with the reality that younger generations have a limited experience in woodcarving, ensuring continuity involves creating appealing opportunities and supportive environments. By uniting efforts and embracing innovative and sustainable

practices, they can overcome these challenges and continue to flourish, ensuring that their rich cultural heritage remains vibrant for future generations.

Keywords: Climate Change, Cultural Heritage, Woodcarving Industry, Paete Laguna

I. INTRODUCTION

Among the many talents bestowed upon the Filipino people is the remarkable ability to craft and invent with their hands, their feet, and their entire beings (Caparas et al., 1991). Throughout the region, the Philippines is proud of its rich heritage of traditional crafts, offering glimpse into the culture and traditions of its people, such as pottery, loom weaving, jewelry crafting, and woodcarving.

Woodcarving is one of the most notable artistic traditions in the Philippines. Since the Spanish era, it has been a thriving wood-based industry for the Filipinos. The small town of Paete in the province of Laguna is recognized as the Carving Capital of the Philippines and is the center of religious and cultural artifacts makers. Here, creating religious arts and craftsmanship are deeply ingrained in the spirit and culture of the Paete woodcarvers (Crimson, 2020).

The Paete woodcarvers have developed and transmitted their skills over the years, producing religious images and cultural artifacts that reflect their heritage and creativity. However, the woodcarving industry and the cultural heritage in Paete Laguna is facing a serious threat due to climate change and its consequences, such as intense monsoons, flooding, landslides, and deforestations. These environmental shifts have prompted the Philippine government to implement a community-based forest management strategies in an effort to safeguard the sustainability of this artistic legacy and the surrounding environment (Tumaneng-Diete, et al., 2005). Moreover, the loss of natural habitat of forest resources as raw materials for the wood carving industry has led to the unsustainable supply and availability of the special wood known as 'Batikuling' (*Litsea leytensis Merr.*). This tree species is preferred by the Paete woodcarvers for its wood quality and durability (Gutierrez et al, 2020). Additionally, the national ban on logging, implemented to prevent further environmental degradation,

has restricted local woodcarvers from sourcing Batikuling from natural forests. Instead, they have resorted to alternative sources of wood from tree species that include gmelina (*Gmelina arborea*), mahogany (*Swietenia mahogani*), and paraiso (*Melia azedarach L.*).

Despite these challenges, the Paete carvers have not given up on their craft and have tried to adapt and cope with the changing conditions. However, there is limited research on how climate change impacts the wood carving industry in Paete Laguna and how the Paete carvers deal with them to sustain and hold the great and historical significance of the Filipino woodcarving industry.

The study's objective is to fill this gap by conducting a qualitative study that will explore the knowledge, perceptions, experiences, and strategies of the Paete carvers regarding climate change and its effects on their industry. The paper will also provide recommendations for enhancing the resilience and sustainability of the wood carving industry in Paete Laguna. This study is significant for contributing to the knowledge and practice of cultural heritage management, as well as for supporting the empowerment and well-being including the sustainability of the Paete carvers and the local community.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The Carving Capital of the Philippines: Paete, Laguna

The town of Paete is situated at the northern part of the province of Laguna and has a land area of 55.02 square kilometers which constitutes 2.85% of the province's total land area. It was instituted in 1580 by Spanish Franciscan Order Priests Juan de Plasencia and Diego de Oropesa. It is believed that the first inhabitants in the town were of Malay ancestry, who traveled from Borneo in their sturdy and quick 'Balangay' boats (Philippines Carving Art, 2013).

The name Paete (pronounced as "Pa-e-te") was derived from the Tagalog word "*paet*" which means "chisel" in English. The fascinating origin story of Paete unfolds during a visit by a young friar to their mission near the lakeshore. As he explored the area, he encountered a skilled woodcarver diligently working with a carving tool called "*Paet*." Curious about the local name, the friar asked the woodcarver how the place was referred to in his language. The woodcarver, assuming the friar was inquiring about the tool, replied, "*Paet po*." When the young friar reported back to his father superior, he proudly declared that he had reached "Paete." And so, from that moment on, the name Paete became etched into the town's history (Crimson, 2020).

Master artisan, Mariano Madrinan, was the official hero of the town, whose *obra maestra*, the life-like Mater Dolorosa received a prestigious award in Amsterdam in 1882. In recognition of this masterpiece, King Alfonso XII of Spain even awarded him a diploma of honor, which was forwarded to Spain's Governor General in the Philippines for personal presentation to Master Mariano in Paete.

By virtue of Proclamation No. 809 series of 2005, Paete, Laguna was declared as the Carving Capital of the Philippines. Paete gained the title because of its rich artistic history and the extraordinary woodcarving abilities of its residents. The Climate Change and Cultural Heritage: A Qualitative Study of the Paete Wood Carvers in
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woodcarvings made by the artisans of Paete are highly sought after due to their unparalleled craftsmanship and meticulous attention to detail (Seevers, 2023).

The majority of Paete carvers are well-known for their depictions of religious figures. During Lent season, religious figures related to Jesus Christ's crucifixion are in high demand, and as Christmas approaches, the focus shifts to nativity scenes, capturing the essence of the birth of Jesus (Cagape, 2019). Beyond religious woodcarvings, the town became known for its wooden shoes (*bakya*), which are beautifully handcrafted and chiseled in a variety of remarkable designs. Interestingly, it is also believed that Paete holds a unique distinction: it may be the birthplace of the modern yo-yo (Mel, 2018). This simple yet captivating toy has a fascinating origin story, and its creation is attributed to this picturesque town.

The Paete woodcarving tradition has a rich and ancient lineage. Each intricately carved piece symbolizes abundance, prosperity, or festive occasions in the region, predating even the Spanish colonization (Sinco, 2021). The exceptional woodwork of Paete's skilled artisans was also acknowledged by the Philippine National Hero, Jose Rizal, in one of his novels. The tradition rooted in time immemorial, endures as a legacy (Seevers, 2023).

Traditional Wood Practices

The market road in the town of Paete is lined with shops that sell a variety of paper mâché and woodworking items. The smell of wood is heavy in the air, mixing with paint and varnish. Open-air workshops for woodcarving are filled with the steady thumping sound of mallets striking chisels. Sawdust is scattered by sporadic wind gusts, fostering an artistic and handcrafted ambiance (Sembrano, 2020). A typical day in this quaint town is defined by the scent of wood and the rhythmic sound of the pounding chisels.

In working with a wood craft, the preparation stage in woodcarving is undoubtedly the most intricate. To create a true masterpiece, one must begin with the right elements. Consider the intended style, whether it will be artistic, realistic, classical, or naïve. Equally crucial is the choice of timber. Woodcarvers opt for wood that has already fought the elements, rather than any random piece from the log pile. A practical starting point is to practice cutting on a common, knot-free softwood timber.

The direction of the grain influences the preferred cutting technique for wood to achieve a smooth finish. Every woodcarver has encountered grain tear out as a result of improper or inefficient wood-cutting techniques. Cutting against the grain, whether perpendicularly or at obliquely, is generally the safer and more manageable course of action, particularly when utilizing slicing cuts. While it can be helpful when roughening out, cutting against the grain can result in uncontrollably large splitting. In holding the tools, employ a light grip in which one hand propels the blade forward in a specific direction while the others guide and modifies the cutting edge's position and depth of cut. The two hands cooperate harmoniously with the strength of the worker and the wood's qualities (WWI, 2022).

Finishing could be complicated because selecting the right finish can elevate the work, breathing life into it. Conversely, an ill-suited finish can ruin the piece that have painstakingly crafted. Once the choice is wrong, removing it can become a daunting task. To avoid such pitfalls, woodcarvers consider creating sample boards using the anticipated finishes. This allows the preview of the result before committing. Additionally, regardless of the finish that is opt for, the woodcarvers meticulously clean up any excess, especially in the intricate details of finely carved pieces.

Cultural Heritage and Climate Change

Cultural Heritage

The term cultural heritage refers to all the important tangible and intangible assets of a particular society and culture. Intangible cultural practices like dance and storytelling are cultural heritages, along with the collections and monuments, complex buildings, and archaeological sites. These kinds of heritage are connected to individual's self-development and community progress, and provide context for historical events, and promote society's wellbeing (Orr et al., 2021).

The United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) has identified a number of factors as threat to cultural heritage, including the changes in temperature, precipitation, atmospheric moisture, wind intensity, desertification, and the interaction between climatic changes and pollution (Sesana et al, 2021). Consequently, cultural resource managers, community leaders, and archaeologists are confronting the reality that anthropogenic climate change is also a major threat to cultural heritage (Hambrecht & Rockman, 2017).

Climate Change

According to Climate Reality Project (2019), the Philippines stands out as the nation most impacted by climate change due to its geographic location with respect to 2013's data of Global Climate Risk Index 2015. The bodies of water surrounding the Philippines, situated in the western Pacific Ocean, are naturally warm and are likely to become even warmer as average sea surface temperature rise. The heat released by the ocean ascends into the sky leading to cloud formation and wind patterns. Over time, the increasing amount of heat released into the atmosphere has resulted in more intense and more frequent storms and have affected the Philippines.

Climate change is presently happening. The evidence presented suggests that the change cannot be explained solely by natural variation. According to Philippine Atmospheric, Geophysical Astronomical Services Administration (PAGASA), the most

recent scientific assessments have confirmed that the observed warming of the climate system since the mid-20th century is most likely caused by anthropogenic activities, such as the use of fossil fuels and land use change. Current warming has posed significant challenges to humans and the environment, and it will continue to do so in the future.

Climate-Related Threats to Woodcarving Industry

Deforestation from Forest Fire

The escalating human activities and climate change are causing wildfires to occur with greater frequency and intensity worldwide. This issue is particularly pressing for forested nations, as wildfires are drastically shrinking forest ecosystems, leading to a catastrophic loss of biodiversity that underpins all ecosystem functions and services, particularly in tropical and subtropical regions (Geraskina et al., 2022). Fires play a significant role in the emission of various trace gases and aerosols, and they are a key factor behind the yearly fluctuations in the concentration of several trace gases, including greenhouse gases like carbon dioxide (CO₂) and methane (CH₄) (Van der Werf et al., 2010).

Many biologists view wildfires as a destructive force to living organisms, potentially causing the permanent extinction of certain species (Geraskina et al., 2022). It impacts plants directly by causing damage or complete destruction, and indirectly by altering their living conditions. The immediate effects of wildfires include the burning of forest matter, soil heating, and the injury or death of plants, vertebrates, soil fauna, and microorganisms. The long-term repercussions involve changes to the soil caused by fire, a decrease in soil biota diversity, desiccation and death of trees, an increase in dead plant matter, and the subsequent succession of vegetation

Houghton, 2012). While some ecosystems may eventually regenerate, the recovery trajectory is often protracted and complex.

In the Philippines, the most critical period for wildfires typically starts in mid-February and extends for about 14 weeks. Over the span from 2001 to 2023, the country experienced a significant loss of tree cover due to fires, amounting to 28.6 thousand hectares (kha). In addition, other factors contributed to a loss of 1.44 million hectares (Mha). The year 2022 was particularly devastating, with 4.25 kha of tree cover lost to fires, accounting for 5.0% of the total tree cover loss that year (Global Forest Watch, 2023).

Furthermore, from the 2001 to 2023 record of Global Forest Watch, the province of Palawan recorded the highest average annual rate of tree cover loss due to fires, with an average of 195 hectares (ha) lost each year. It is followed by the average annual rate of tree cover loss due to fires of Agusan del Sur (85 ha), Eastern Samar (83 ha), Davao Oriental (82 ha), Dinagat Islands (77 ha), Surigao del Sur (63 ha), Tawi-Tawi (55 ha), Zamboanga del Norte (43 ha), Quezon (36 ha), and Surigao del Norte (36 ha). These data underscore the significant impact of wildfires on the Philippines' natural landscapes.

Wildfires also lead to significant losses in wood biomass, either through complete combustion or partial damage. The economic value of timber resources also declines due to fire damage to tree trunks and subsequent harm from wind, fungi, and insects. Intense wildfires, with flames reaching heights of 6–8 meters, can render trees nonviable (Geraskina et al., 2022).

In the aftermath of a severe wildfire, the quality of small and medium-sized timber deteriorates rapidly, rendering it unsuitable for industrial use. The growth rate of surviving trees slows, and the lower layers of vegetation suffer damage. These

effects extend to the economy, as the costs associated with timber harvesting and reforestation rise, leading to market instability. Additionally, wildfires can alter the species composition within forests and shift the locations of raw material sources, consequently affecting the supply of raw materials to markets. These changes highlight the far-reaching consequences of wildfires on both the environment and the economy (Geraskina et al., 2022).

Recognizing these undesirable outcomes, the Philippine government took steps to mitigate the loss of forest resources. According to the Society of the Filipino Foresters, Inc., the Philippine government, in collaboration with a diverse group of stakeholders, has undertaken policy efforts to promote sustainable forest management through consultations and action planning to support legislation. The Sustainable Forest Management (SFM) bill was passed in the Lower House with backing from the Society of Filipino Foresters, Inc. (SFFI), a forest governance project funded by the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. This bill aims to bolster the sustainable production of forest resources to revive the forest and wood-based industry in the Philippines, which includes wood carving.

Batikuling (Litsea leytensis Merr.) Endemism

Litsea leytensis is a large tree species belongs to family Lauraceae and is locally known as Batikuling. It is found in the forests at low and medium altitudes on Luzon, particularly in the province of Laguna, Bataan, Sorsogon, and Quezon (ERDB-DENR, 2017). The tree reaches a height of about 25 meters with a diameter of 80 cm. Its bark is a pale brown to gray, about 1 cm thick, ridged or wrinkled, while its inner bark is yellowish. The leaves of the tree are simple, alternate, lanceolate to oblong in shape, have a shiny green surface and glaucous underneath (ERDB-DENR, 2017). The wood of this species is considered economically valuable because it is preferred

to use in general housing, building materials, plywood and veneer, musical instruments, furniture and handicrafts (Engay-Gutierrez et al., 2023).

Batikuling holds a special place in the world of Paete woodcarving as it is a favorite wood of the artisans due its unique blend of hardness and softness. Its resistance with insects and fungal attacks makes it an excellent choice for carving. For over a century, the skilled artisans of Paete have crafted countless statuaries, architectural embellishments, and souvenirs out of batikuling wood that became popular worldwide (Gutierrez et al., 2020).

Unfortunately, the tree became one of the threatened forest tree species in the Philippines due to continuous declining of its population (IUCN, 2020). The limited supply of the wood, to an extent that it became critical, established the batikuling tree as vulnerable species on the International Union for Conservation and Nature (IUCN) Red List of Threatened Species and as an endangered species under DAO 2007-01, which means that survival in the wild is impossible with the persistence of various causal factors (Gutierrez et al., 2020).

Since 2010, the scarcity of Batikuling has posed significant challenges to Paete artisans. The threats to Batikuling are manifold, with the primary concern being the loss of its natural habitat. The species' survival is jeopardized by the conversion of forests for agricultural purposes, the clearing of land for urban development, and the extraction of forest resources for commercial gain (IUCN, 2020). These activities not only reduce the available habitat but also degrade the quality of the remaining areas, making it difficult for the species to thrive. Thus, cutting of Batikuling in public domain's natural and residual forest was strictly prohibited according to Executive Order No. 23, Declaring a Moratorium on the Cutting and Harvesting of Timber in the Natural and Residual Forests and Creating the Anti-Illegal Logging Task Force.

In the recent study of Engay-Guiterrez (2023), titled *Predicting species occurrence of Litsea leytensis Merr. in the provinces of Laguna and Quezon, Philippines*, the occurrence of Batikuling was mostly determined by climatic factors, edaphic, and anthropogenic variables. Due to an extreme weather event experienced by the Philippines and the anthropogenic variables such as land use and land cover changes of the human population, logging and the kaingin system of agriculture, Batikuling faces habitat threatening.

Supporting this concern, the 2021 Global Forest Watch Analysis reported a loss of 142,070 hectares of tree cover in the provinces where Batikuling is found, spanning from 2001 to 2020. This loss is indicative of a broader trend of deforestation that continues to threaten the species. The IUCN in 2022 further highlighted the ongoing decline, with high forest loss statistics continuing to be recorded in recent years.

Batikuling, with its legacy carried forth by the skilled woodcarvers of Paete, remains a testament to artistic craftsmanship. These talented artisans transform this remarkable wood into timeless works of art. However, beyond the realm of artistry, the species holds significance for both large and small-scale industries. Whether as raw wood or tree parts, or as extractives for manufacturing and processing, Batikuling deserves recognition and preservation. (Razal et al., 2004).

III. STATEMENT OF THE STUDY

The traditional woodcarving industry in Paete, Laguna, is a testament to the Filipino people's rich cultural heritage and artistic skill. However, this industry is currently facing significant challenges due to the adverse effects of climate change, including extreme weather conditions and deforestation. These environmental changes have led to a scarcity of Batikuling wood, the preferred material for Paete woodcarvers, due to over-extraction and the loss of its natural habitat. This study aims to examine the impact of these environmental challenges on the woodcarving industry and the adaptive strategies of the Paete carvers. The problem is compounded by the lack of research on the intersection of climate change and traditional industries, making it crucial to investigate and provide recommendations for the resilience and sustainability of the Paete woodcarving industry.

IV. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objective of this study was to conduct a qualitative study that explored the knowledge, perceptions, experiences, and strategies of the Paete carvers regarding climate change and its effects on their industry.

The study specifically aimed to achieve the following:

1. Determine the knowledge, perceptions, and skills of Paete wood carvers related to climate-change and its impacts on the wood carving industry (e.g. cultural knowledge, skills, and artistic traditions),
2. Analyze how climate change influences livelihoods, economic sustainability, market demand for Paete wood carvings,
3. Investigate how Paete wood carvers adopt innovative techniques, materials, and artistic processes in response to changing weather and climatic conditions, and,
4. Assess the resilience of the Paete wood carving community in the face of climate-related challenges, while preserving their cultural identity and heritage.

V. RATIONALE

The purpose of this qualitative research is to delve into the knowledge, perceptions, experiences, and strategies of the Paete carvers, with the aim of understanding how they navigate the challenges posed by climate change on their cultural heritage. By documenting these insights, the study will contribute to the fields of cultural heritage management and environmental sustainability. Furthermore, it will offer recommendations to enhance the resilience of the woodcarving industry in Paete, thereby supporting the empowerment, well-being, and sustainability of the local artisans and their community.

This research is significant as it not only aims to preserve a vital aspect of Filipino cultural identity but also addresses the broader implications of environmental changes on traditional industries. The findings will provide valuable contributions to policymakers, cultural practitioners, and environmental conservationists.

VI. SCOPE AND LIMITATIONS

The scope of this study was the rich cultural heritage of Paete, Laguna, with a particular emphasis on its renowned woodcarving industry. The study delved into the distinctive craftsmanship, techniques, and artistic skills that are unique of Paete's artisans. Additionally, the research examined how the repercussions of climate change challenged the woodcarving industry. It further investigated the collective knowledge, experiences, perceptions, and adaptive strategies that the Paete artisans employ to preserve their cultural heritage amidst these adversities.

Employing a qualitative research methodology, the study provided profound insights, although it may not provide results that are statistically presented. Constraints in practicality led to a limited sample size, comprising participants engaged in individual interviews and focus group discussions. The study's scope was further constrained by the potential limitations in the availability and accuracy of data procured from municipal offices, because of recently transitioned to a computerized system. Moreover, the insights gained from the study are deeply rooted in the local traditions, values, and social structures of the Paete woodcarving community. Therefore, while the findings provide valuable information about this particular community, they may not translate well to different groups with different cultural backgrounds or to broader contexts outside of this specific setting. Researchers and practitioners should consider this limitation when trying to extend the findings to different contexts or generalize them to a broader population.

VII. DESCRIPTION OF THE STUDY AREA

Geographical Profile

Paete is classified as a fourth-class municipality within the province of Laguna, Philippines. This inland municipality is nestled in the northern region of Laguna and is situated approximately 113 kilometers from Manila when traveling via the Sta. Cruz route, and around 90 kilometers via the Siniloan – Pililia – Cainta route.

The town is flanked by the Municipality of Pakil to the north, the Municipality of Kalayaan to the south, the Province of Quezon to the east, and the Laguna de Bay to the west. Its coordinates are set at 14 degrees 22' latitude and 121 degrees 29' longitude. Geographically, Paete has a roughly rectangular shape, featuring hilly terrain on its eastern portion and a flatter landscape to the west.

Spanning a total land area of 6,301.625 hectares, which includes the Sierra Madre Mountain uplands, Paete's urban center, known as Población, covers just 201.861 hectares. The town is divided into nine barangays, all located within Población: namely Ibaba del Sur, Maytoong, Ermita, Quinale, Ilaya del Sur, Ilaya del Norte, Bagumbayan, Bangkusay, and Ibaba del Norte (Figure 1). The mountainous regions are further segmented into sitios, each administratively linked to the nearest urban barangay.

Figure 1. Map of the Municipality of Paete, Laguna.

Source: MDRRM Office

As per the 2022 census, Paete has a population of 28,515, placing it among the 1,073 Philippine cities and municipalities with a population greater than 10,000 but not exceeding 50,000. The census also projects a population increase to 29,000 by 2023. The town has 7,137 households, with an average of five individuals per household.

Biophysical Characteristics

Topography

Paete is predominantly mountainous, with 90% of its land being hilly and a small plain near Laguna de Bay. The town center, Población, lies at a lower elevation, separated from the higher uplands by a steep slope. The uplands, at 300-500 meters above sea level, contrast with the flat lowlands prone to flooding from Laguna de Bay during heavy rains. Development is limited to areas with less than 15% slope due to erosion risks, with only 7% of the land suitable for farming and construction. Paete's Climate Change and Cultural Heritage: A Qualitative Study of the Paete Wood Carvers in the Philippines...

soil varies, with hydrosols near the bay supporting fish culture, clay loam in the lowlands and uplands, and mountain soil covering most of the eastern uplands.

Forest Resources

In Paete, 15% of the land, or about 945 hectares, is dedicated to agriculture, predominantly coconut plantations found in the uplands, along with citrus and various fruit trees such as duhat, guava, lanzones, jackfruit, santol, mango, and star apple. The region also has 33% of its area, approximately 2,080 hectares, as cultivated land, and grasslands where crops like sitao, eggplant, gabi, coffee, papaya, and kamoteng kahoy are grown, amidst grasses and shrubs like T-grass, barnyard grass, mutha, and luya-luyahan. Nearly 45% of Paete features open canopy areas with mature trees and ornamental plants grown for their aesthetic leaves, flowers, or fruits, including lily, gumamela, mussaenda, dieffenbachia, corazon de maria, and duranta. Undergrowth in these areas includes common herbs and shrubs like bugos and coronitas, as well as vines and ferns such as baging and pako, complementing the softwood species like batino, balete, tibig, malapapaya, binuga, malasaging, and malakamias.

Protected areas cover 40% of Paete's 6,302.625 hectares are constrained from development. The University of the Philippines Land Grant includes a 1,900-hectare tract at the town's eastern edge is difficult to access. Originally the land was intended as a dairy farm, but now it explores options like campus expansion and reforestation. Additionally, around 300 hectares fall within the Caliraya-Lumot Watershed, safeguarded by the National Integrated Protected Areas System Act. Another 300 hectares of steep terrain are designated solely for forestation projects and unsuitable for building due to slopes over 30% (MENRO, Paete).

Climate

According to the Local Climate Change Action Plan (LCCAP) 2021-2026 of Paete, Laguna, Paete's climate is classified as Type III based to Modification Corona's system as adopted by Philippine Atmospheric, Geophysical and Astronomical Services Administration (PAGASA), meaning rainfall is fairly even throughout the year, leading to its nickname "*Pusali ng Langit.*" It has a brief dry season from February to April. Protected from the northeast monsoon but open to the southwest monsoon and tropical cyclone rains. Paete sees daily rainfall from May to December, peaking in July to October. Temperatures range from an average high of 31°C in during May to a low of 22°C in January, with an annual average of 28.7°C.

VIII. METHODOLOGY

This study employed a qualitative research design to explore the knowledge, experiences, perspectives, and adaptive strategies of Paete woodcarvers in the face of climate change.

Data Collection Method

The study conducted an in-depth one-on-one interview with 14 key informants, including local government employees, business owners, and selected Paete carvers, who possessed valuable historical knowledge and experience of the wood carving industry. The interview used an open-ended question encouraging the participants detailed responses. There were two sets of focal group discussions involving residents of Paete. The first set consisted of 15 persons who are directly and indirectly involved in the woodcarving industry, and the second set consisted of 13 persons from the community's younger generation, including both genders. The discussions were conducted separately. It facilitated a dialogue of shared experiences related to climate change and collective perspectives. Secondary information was obtained from local institution such as municipal offices (e.g. Planning and Development Office, Environment and Natural Resources Office, Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Office, and Tourism and Cultural Heritage Office). Participants were selected based on their expertise, involvement in wood carving, and knowledge of cultural heritage.

Data Gathering Process

A semi-structured interview was used for the in-depth interviews with participants with different community roles to gather diverse perspectives. The interview was guided with the questions related to climate change, resource availability, including the coping mechanism, and adaptive practices of the Paete wood

carvers, and the cultural significance of wood carving. All the observed activities, materials and tools, and the work environment were recorded and documented.

Data Analysis

The data analysis for this study employed a thematic analysis. Each interview was audio-recorded and transcribed verbatim to ensure accuracy in data representation. All the transcribed interviews were read multiple times to familiarize with the content. Initial codes were generated inductively, directly from the data and collated into potential themes by grouping related codes together. For instance, codes from the interview such as *'wala na halos na inuukit na kahoy'* (Almost no wood is suitable for carving), *'iyong ibang mag-uukit dumadayo na sa abroad'* (Several wood carvers are heading overseas) and *'shutdown ang industriya namin noong pandemic'* (Our industry was shut down during the pandemic), were combined under the broader theme of 'Climate Change Influences on Livelihoods, Economic sustainability, and Market demand for Paete Woodcarvings' (See Appendix E). The identified themes were reviewed and refined to ensure they accurately represent the data. The final step involved the writing up of the findings, integrating the narrative of the participant's knowledge, experiences, perceptions, and adaptive strategies, while maintaining a strong connection to the secondary data obtained from the municipal offices. Visual presentation such as tables, charts and graphs were employed to effectively convey the data derived from the interview.

IX. RESULTS

Data Presentation of the Interviewee's Profile

Table 1

The Socio-Demographic Profile of the Participants

	<i>n=14 (100%)</i>
<i>Participant's Age, M (SD), years</i>	48.1 (8.77)
<i>Gender, M (SD)</i>	1.07 (0.27)
<i>Male</i>	13
<i>Female</i>	1
<i>Marital Status, M (SD)</i>	1.29 (0.47)
<i>Single</i>	4
<i>Married</i>	10
<i>Educational attainment, M (SD)</i>	3.29 (0.61)
<i>Primary Level</i>	1
<i>Secondary Level</i>	8
<i>Tertiary Level (College)</i>	5
<i>Community Role, M (SD)</i>	5.14 (0.66)
<i>Local official</i>	-
<i>Non-government organization</i>	-
<i>Religious leader</i>	-
<i>Business owner</i>	2
<i>Skilled worker</i>	8
<i>Local government employee</i>	4
<i>Years of experience in woodcarving, M (SD)</i>	19.9 (15.8)
<i>Average Monthly Income, M (SD)</i>	9.43 (2.41)

Table 1 shows that among the participants of the one-on-one interview, mostly are male (92.9%), married (71.4%), completed secondary education (57.1%), and skilled workers (57.1%).

Woodcarvers in the town have an extensive experience in woodcarving. Figure 2 demonstrates that the maximum tenure of woodcarving experience among the participants is 50 years, attributed to a Paete artisan. He began his journey in the craft at the tender age of 9, initially experimenting with a chisel and carving. In stark contrast, local government employees have no practical experience in the woodcarving industry. While they possess theoretical knowledge of woodcarving, they have never been actively involved in the practice.

Figure 2. Years of experience of the participants in the woodcarving industry.

Conversely, Figure 3 illustrates that the highest recorded monthly income, amounting to Php50,000.00, is earned by a business owner in the town. The lowest average monthly income reported by another participant is Php3,000.00, This skilled worker has been engaged in the woodcarving industry for the past 9 years, however not as a full-time worker. This demonstrates that woodcarvers, despite their skill and contribution to the industry, tend to receive a relatively low income.

Figure 3. Average monthly income of the participants.

X. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Knowledge, Experiences, Perceptions, and Skills of Paete Woodcarvers related to Climate Change

Knowledge and Experiences of Paete Woodcarvers

In the quaint town of Paete, where the chisel's dance with wood is a language of its own, the woodcarvers hold a profound knowledge of climate change's impacts on their revered craft. The interviews and focus group discussion indicate that the participants are well-informed about climate change and its repercussions. They have personally witnessed a range of adverse effects, such as intense heatwaves that warp and crack their medium. They have experienced heavy floods brought by the rising water level from Laguna de Bay during Typhoon Ondoy in 2009, which disrupted their work and damaged their materials. Furthermore, the global pandemic caused by COVID-19 led the closure of their industry, resulting in widespread of economic disruptions and job losses. Additionally, they are aware of the effects of climate-related hazards such as flooding, landslide, forest fires, illegal logging, and deforestation on the availability of a steady wood supply, which is crucial for the continuation of their cultural heritage of woodcarving.

Figure 4 illustrates the data on level of awareness of the interviewees on climate change gathered during the interview. It highlights that participants exhibit a high level of awareness regarding climate change, with an average awareness score of 8.21 and a standard deviation of 0.21. This statistical evidence suggests that the interviewees are well-informed about climate change issues.

Figure 4. Level of awareness on climate change of the interviewees.

Rainfall-Induced Flooding

Paete’s climate, shaped by its proximity to hills and lakes, is prone to flooding due to factors identified by PAGASA, such as sustained or heavy rainfall overwhelming the drainage system, and water overflow from nearby bodies of water.

The wet season that starts in latter part of May continuing through November, brings about the most dramatic changes to Paete’s landscape. These rains are not uniform; they vary in their duration, frequency, and intensity. Historically, the heaviest rains occurring in July, August, and September (Figure 5). The average monthly precipitation during these months was recorded at 320.5 mm, 191.6 mm, and 454.4 mm, respectively. In contrast, minimal rainfall, was recorded as little as 15mm during the dry season (LCCAP, Paete).

The pattern of rainfall has significant implications for the region’s agriculture, as it dictates the planting and harvesting schedules and the types of crops that can be grown. Crops have specific water requirements, and those that are suited to the region’s rainfall regime are more likely to thrive.

Figure 5. Precipitation amount in Paete, Laguna.

Source: Meteoblue

In 2009, Typhoon Ondoy had a significant impact on the water level of Laguna de Bay. According to the report, the lake's water level rose to within 15cm of its 2009 water level during the typhoon, which brought devastating floods to towns around the lake in Laguna, including Paete. The normal water level for Laguna de Bay is at 12.5 meters from September to December, and at 10.5 meters during the dry season (Laguna Lake Development Authority). However, according to the Inquirer news report (2012), during Ondoy, the water level increased to 13.8 meters above sea level. This was close to breaching the 13.95-meter mark that was recorded during the height of the typhoon.

The flooding affected many people, with reports indicating that around 217,420 people in Laguna were impacted (Relief Web, 2009). The Paete recorded the highest number of affected families (1,444 families) according to the municipal data. The

floodwaters were so high that they reached waist level, forcing residents to halt their work for months. Homes and woodcraft shops sustained partially damaged disrupting the livelihoods of the community. These effects were experienced by the residents and woodcarving industry located along shores of Laguna de Bay. The flood persisted for a lengthy period of six months, during which affected families had to reside in evacuation centers. Throughout this challenging time, the woodcarving industry and local livelihoods were supported with the provision of relief goods.

The situation was so critical that even with fair weather, the swollen Laguna de Bay posed a threat of repeating the 2009 flooding because the town is likely to experience wetter seasons in the coming years as the International Panel on Climate Change Studies cite that increases in temperature catalyze evaporation, leading to heavier precipitation. The interviewees also associated that the severity of the flooding was compounded by garbage and wastes that were thrown in the lake and an outdated drainage system of the town, which could have contributed to higher water levels and exacerbated the flooding.

Rainfall-Induced Landslide

Landslides are indeed another significant natural hazard that can impact the town of Paete. They occur when the stability of a slope fails, resulting in the movement of rock, debris, or earth down the slope, primarily driven by the force of gravity. Factors contributing to landslides include the slope's material properties, water content, and changes in the environment, such as deforestation or earthquakes.

In the Sierra Madre Mountain area, landslides have historically been triggered by the onset of the rainy season. The saturation of the soil from continuous rain can weaken the hill slopes and lead to landslides. This poses a risk to infrastructure, such as the national road that traverses through Paete and the neighboring town of

Kalayaan in Laguna, making it vulnerable to blockages and damage from landslides (LCCAP, Paete).

In worst case scenario, according to Municipal's Contingency Plan, the western barangays of Paete, which are situated near the slopes of the Sierra Madre, are particularly at risk. If there is continuous rainfall for 5-10 days, 25% of this area could be severely affected by landslides. The consequences of such events can be extensive, potentially leading to property damage, disruption of transportation and communication networks, loss of their livelihood, and, most critically, threats to human safety.

Extreme Heat-Induced Fire

Fires can result from different factors, including high temperatures, prolonged exposure to sunlight, or the ignition of flammable materials due to extreme heat conditions. For instance, during scorching heatwaves, dry vegetation and combustible materials in forests become more susceptible to catching fire spontaneously.

In the Cordillera region, which encompasses the upland areas of Paete town, the first three months of 2019 were marked by a series of devastating forest fires. Over 140,000 hectares of forest were affected, with a staggering 90 incidents reported (Dumlao, 2019). This information was validated by the head chief of the Municipal Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (MDRRM) of Paete, Mr. Albert Noceja, during an interview.

Mr. Noceja, the head chief, confirmed that one such fire occurred in the uninhabited upland areas of Paete. The fire primarily damaged bamboo trees, which are known for their fast growth and high density. There were no reports affecting the locals of Paete, however, the impact of such a fire is not limited to the immediate vicinity. The destruction of bamboo forests can lead to soil erosion, loss of habitat for

wildlife, and disruption of the forest woods that can sustain the industry of woodcarving. Moreover, the smoke and ash from the fire can have health implications for nearby communities and contribute to air pollution (Gibbens & McKeever, 2023).

The skilled artisans of Paete have come to understand that the increasing intensity of such extreme weather events is not isolated incidents. These are also threatening their chosen medium and their work environment.

Perceptions of the Paete Woodcarvers

Insights gathered from interviews and focus group discussions reveal that Paete's residents are experiencing the repercussions of climate change. The participants express a shared concern over the dwindling wood supply, which is a direct consequence of the altered climate patterns. They observe that the once-abundant forests that supplied their carving materials are now under siege from both human activity and the changing climate. There is a consensus that climate change is profoundly influencing their livelihood, especially concerning the accessibility of essential raw materials for traditional woodcarving. The loss of trees due to higher temperatures and deforestation means that the raw materials they depend on are not only harder to come by but also more expensive, further straining the narrow profit margins of the carvers.

For generations, the woodcarvers have revered wood not merely as a medium but as a vital component of their culture. Wood's cultural uses have been closely linked to human activities throughout the history. Unlike stone, bronze, and iron, which have each marked distinct periods of human advancement, wood has had a persistent and intimate connection with human societies (Kim & Singh, 2016). This is particularly evident in the artisans of Paete, whose millennia-long relationship with wood is captured in wooden cultural heritage. Wooden cultural heritage embodies human life

and values, reflecting the artistic, utilitarian, spiritual, and traditional importance of wood in their cultures. It is a tribute to human ingenuity and creativity, illustrating the diverse ways in which wood has been fashioned, sculpted, and cherished over time (Kim & Singh, 2016).

The shortage of wood leads to the gradual erosion of their traditional knowledge and artistic skills. Consequently, the artisans are forced to turn to alternative materials such as resin, Styrofoam, and plaster of Paris. While these materials enable continued production, for the Paete artisans, they lack the authentic qualities and cultural significance of wood, resulting in creations that are perceived as less genuine and, therefore, less valued.

Skills of the Paete Woodcarvers

Historically, woodcarving has been a significant part of the school activities in the town, particularly when the supply of wood was abundant. Students were introduced to wood crafts at an early age, with elementary schools incorporating woodcraft projects into their programs. By the time students reached secondary education, the process of woodcarving was taught as a form of practical arts. This early exposure to the craft is likely a contributing factor to the high level of skill exhibited by today's artisans.

However, due to the depletion of wood supplies, educators and artisans have had to adapt by turning to alternative materials for carving. Materials such as clay and soap have become popular substitutes, allowing the tradition of carving to continue despite the scarcity of wood. These alternative mediums not only preserve the art of carving but also encourage creativity and innovation in the field.

Today, carving remains a part of educational programs, though with a broader range of materials. This shift reflects a response to environmental concerns and the

need for sustainable practices in the arts. The evolution of the medium used in carving education demonstrates the adaptability of the craft and its practitioners to changing circumstances, ensuring that the art form continues to thrive for future generations.

Paete is also a diverse array of master carvers that bring life to wood with their exceptional skills. Among them are artisans whose specialty lies in the delicate and complex designs of doors, their handiwork adorning the portals of churches, standing as silent witnesses to the country's rich past. The town also boasts an artists gifted in resembling a horse that even the tiniest piece of wood is transformed under their hands into a majestic woodcraft. Another carvers have gained acclaim for their symbolic carabao sculptures, emblematic of the Boy Scouts of the Philippines, meticulously crafted from the aromatic santol wood (See Appendix G). It is their innate talent and expansive imagination that have earned them renown, with each creation encapsulating their individual fame in a single, exquisite piece of art.

The ability to craft through imagination is one of the exceptional skills possessed by the woodcarvers to innovate yet, this artistic skill is also vulnerable to the significant threat of climate change. The interviewees acknowledge that climate change is a formidable obstacle to maintaining the integrity of their craft and the value of their artistic work. They describe a cascading effect resulting from the wood shortage: it reduces the opportunities for skilled craftsmen to practice their trade, which in turn leads to decreased income for their families, and threatening the survival of their time-honored craft.

Influence of Climate Change on Livelihoods, Economic Sustainability, and Market Demand

Recent discussions with focus groups and key informants have shed light on the multifaceted impact of climate change beyond the environment. Climate change

also poses a complex socio-economic challenge that affects livelihoods, economic sustainability, and market demands. The changing climate patterns have led to unpredictable weather conditions, affecting the industry, altering resource availability, and consequently, influencing market trends. As a result, individuals and industries alike are forced to adapt changes, re-evaluating traditional practices and exploring new strategies to ensure economic resilience in the face of this global phenomenon.

Climate Change Impact on Livelihoods

About 80% of the residents of Paete depend directly or indirectly in woodcarving industry (LCCAP, Paete). The financial landscape of the artisans varies significantly between different roles. Skilled workers employed by shops earn an average monthly income of PHP 12,000.00, which reflects the structured but limited earning potential of hired labor. Despite their extensive experience and expertise in wood carving, these workers are often underappreciated. Many choose to accept lower wages to ensure a steady income for their families.

In contrast, artisans who operate independently enjoy the flexibility of managing their own schedules and creative choices. However, this autonomy comes with the uncertainty of income, which fluctuates based on customer demand. Like their employed counterparts, many independent artisans are compelled to accept lower-priced orders to maintain a consistent income stream for their families. Figure 6 illustrates this comparison: (Top) Zaldy Coronel, aged 63, with 50 years of experience in woodcarving, and works independently, earns monthly income of Php10,000 while (Bottom) Nestor Daguitan, aged 58, with 30 years of experience in woodcarving, and employed by shops, earns monthly income of Php12,000.

Figure 6. Woodcarvers of Paete, Laguna who were interviewed.

On the entrepreneurial end, owners of small-scale wood carving businesses typically earn between PHP 25,000 to PHP 50,000 monthly. Many of these entrepreneurs started their journey as skilled carvers and transitioned into business ownership, motivated by the desire for financial stability that exceeds what they could earn as employees. Beyond the local market, these entrepreneurs also attempt on the sale and export of their masterpieces. Their aspiration is to show their creativity, Climate Change and Cultural Heritage: A Qualitative Study of the Paete Wood Carvers in 34 the Philippines...

craftsmanship, and unique designs both domestically and internationally to attract buyers and to showcase their artistry beyond Paete's borders.

Despite their aspirations and talents, these small enterprises face significant challenges in establishing a strong local market presence. They contend with intense competition, changing consumer tastes, and the increasing prevalence of digital marketplaces (Bayocot, 2021). Lacking the resources to compete on a larger scale or invest in effective marketing, these businesses struggle to increase their visibility. Moreover, the shift towards modern décor preferences and the convenience of online shopping threaten to sideline traditional crafts like wood carving.

Climate Change Impact on Economic Sustainability

Climatic Variations

The Batikuling tree, a vital species for the woodcarving industry in Paete, Laguna, flourishes in low to medium altitudes and is well-suited to Type II and Type III climates. According to Global Biodiversity Information Facility, this tree is found in various locations within Laguna province, such as Pangil, Lumban, Paete, and Siniloan, as well as in Tayabas, Real, and Infanta in Quezon province (Engay-Gutierrez, 2023). Research indicates that the presence of Batikuling is significantly influenced by climatic conditions (62.0%), soil characteristics (21.76%), human activities (9.53%), topography (5.15%), and surrounding vegetation (1.34%) (Engay-Gutierrez, 2023).

Figure 7 provides a clear visual breakdown of the different environmental and anthropogenic factors that affect the presence of Batikuling, indicating that climatic conditions are by far the most significant.

Figure 7. Factors affecting the occurrence of Batikuling tree (*Litsea leytensis* Merr.).

Despite Paete’s Type III climate, which is generally favorable for Batikuling, the town is currently experiencing climatic variations that could impact the tree’s growth. The dry season brings reduced rainfall and temperatures ranging from above 20°C to over 30°C and in wet season, the precipitation is non-uniform, exhibiting variations in duration, frequency, and intensity. According to PAGASA’s climate projections, Paete is expected to encounter a temperature rise of 2.0°C to 2.4°C in the coming years, particularly from March to August, with the possibility of more days exceeding 35°C. Such climatic shifts could have profound effects on the region’s natural resources and the thriving woodcarving industry, potentially challenging the sustainability of Batikuling as a key raw material.

The average temperatures and precipitation in Paete, Laguna are graphically presented in Figure 8. The solid line represents the mean daily maximum temperature for each month in Paete. It shows the average highest temperature reached during an average day. Similarly, the solid blue line represents the mean daily minimum temperature. This line indicates the average lowest temperature

experienced during a typical day. The dashed red and blue lines correspond to hot days (hottest day of the month) and cold nights (coldest night of the month) over the past 30 years.

Figure 8. Average temperatures and precipitation in Paete, Laguna.

Source: Meteoblue

Deforestation from Forest Fires

Climate change also plays a significant role in the acceleration of deforestation. Catastrophic weather events, such as wildfires are destroying millions of hectares of forests each year, and are becoming more severe as global warming progresses (Nasi et al., 2002). The forests in Southeast Asia are particularly at risk, with an alarming trend of increased fire susceptibility (Santosa & Utami, 2020).

The provinces of Laguna and Quezon in the Philippines have experienced significant environmental challenges. Notably, areas known for their dense Batikuling tree populations have suffered a substantial loss of forest area (Figure 9). Specifically, 123 hectares of forest land have been destroyed by fires from 2001 to 2023, as Climate Change and Cultural Heritage: A Qualitative Study of the Paete Wood Carvers in the Philippines...

reported by Global Forest Watch Analysis. These wildfires have been a persistent threat, leading to the degradation of these vital woodlands. They have not only caused extensive ecological damage but also led to the displacement of diverse species, contributed to increased carbon emissions, and exacerbated the effects of global warming. The repercussions of these wildfires extend beyond environmental loss as they profoundly affect local communities that depend on forest resources for their economic sustenance.

Figure 9. Tree cover loss across specific regions in Laguna and Quezon.

The gradual depletion of wood supplies, particularly the endemic Batikuling wood, caused by climatic variations and deforestation from forest fires have led to a marked escalation in the cost of raw materials for woodcarving. Batikuling wood is prized for its exceptional quality and durability and lifespan that can extend over a century before showing signs of decay. Due to its superior attributes, crafts made from Batikuling are priced higher than those made from other woods like mahogany, santol,

kamagong, and narra. Currently, one board foot of Batikuling wood costs Php50.00 – Php75.00 which is higher than the cost of mahogany wood at Php25.00 per board foot. This price difference reflects the value placed on Batikuling’s quality and the difficulty in sourcing it.

The impact of these environmental challenge is not just ecological but also cultural and economic. The woodcarving industry, which relies heavily on Batikuling, faces a crisis as the raw material becomes increasingly rare and expensive. The search for alternative woods is a complex issue. While mahogany, camagong, narra, tangile, lauan, jackfruit, and santol are potential substitutes, they present difficulties due to their hardness, making the carving process more labor-intensive and less conducive to the intricate design’s characteristic of traditional woodcarving. This shift not only affects the ease of production but also the aesthetic and cultural authenticity of the carvings.

Figure 10. Crafts made from different kinds of wood.

Source: (1) Woodcraft made from Batikuling wood and was captured from a mini gallery of Tourism Office, Paete laguna. (2) Woodcraft made from mahogany wood. (3) Woodcraft made from santol wood. Image (2) and (3) were captured from Galaboc

Shop in Paete, Laguna.

The decreasing supply of timber has created a challenge for artisans in obtaining high-quality wood. The situation is exacerbated by the stringent documentation required for the lawful felling of trees. The process of legally cutting trees involves a complex set of documents. This includes securing a tree cutting permit which requires a letter request, inventory report, cutting plan, development plan, environmental compliance certificate, and other documents (DENR DAO No. 2021-11). While these requirements are designed to promote sustainable use of forest resources and protect the environment, they can pose significant challenges for woodcraft producers. The complexity and time involved in securing these documents can be burdensome, especially for small-scale artisans who may not have the resources or expertise to navigate the bureaucratic process. This can lead to delays and increased costs, impacting their ability to produce and sell their crafts.

The rigorous documentation process underscores the government's commitment to sustainable forestry practices. However, it also highlights the need for a more streamlined process that can protect the environment while also supporting the livelihoods of local woodcraft producers. Simplifying the permit process or providing assistance to artisans in completing these requirements could be beneficial steps towards achieving this balance.

The Officer-in-Charge of the Municipal Environment and Natural Resources Office (OIC-MENRO), Ms. Nancy Cagayan, has verified that they issue recommendation certificates to Paete residents who seek to acquire wood. However, it is important to note that these recommendation certificates are intended solely for construction purposes and not for woodcarving activities. Subsequently, the actual

processing of these documents takes place at the City Environment and Natural Resources Office (CENRO) located in Sta. Cruz, Laguna.

The Head of the Municipal Planning and Development Committee of Paete, Engr. Jeriel Cadapan, confirmed that in 2005 during the President Gloria Macapagal Administration, they were granted an exemption from the logging ban to sustain the woodcarving industry in the town. However, this permit was subsequently revoked due to the continuous resurgence of illegal logging activities in areas like the Sierra Madre Mountain Range (Bicker, 2023). The local government of Paete made concerted efforts to secure an exemption from the country's total log ban for their woodcarving industry, recognizing its cultural significance and economic necessity. However, despite these initiatives, the strict enforcement of the policy meant that their requests were consistently denied, leaving the artisans to navigate the challenges of maintaining their craft under these constraints.

Despite these restrictions, the local government acknowledged that the woodcarvers of Paete have established connections with various suppliers who provide them with the necessary materials for their craft. These suppliers are crucial for the continuation of the woodcarving industry in Paete.

The timber supply for Paete carvers is predominantly sourced from Quezon Province, which operates on a centralized model of timber procurement. This centralization means that most of the timber, particularly species like Batikuling, is sourced from this area (Engay-Gutierrez et al, 2023). However, this province has faced significant challenges with illegal logging, which not only depletes the forest resources but also undermines efforts towards sustainable forest management.

The reliance on a single source for timber can be risky. If Quezon Province faces issues such as environmental disasters, stricter regulations, or depletion of

resources, it could lead to interruptions in the timber supply. This would have a ripple effect on industries that depend on this timber, such as the woodcarving industry.

In contrast, the lack of suppliers in Laguna could be attributed to a couple of factors. One possibility is that the forest resources in Laguna are not as abundant, which limits the amount of timber that can be sourced sustainably. Another reason could be the presence of more stringent environmental laws that restrict logging activities. Yet, these laws are in place to protect the remaining forest resources and prevent the negative impacts of deforestation.

Figure 11. Mahogany wood supply from Quezon, Province.

Faced with these adversities, the woodcarvers of Paete are compelled to explore alternative means of income, such as farming, carpentry, and putting up a small sari-sari store. Meanwhile, some descendants of these artisans have carved a place for themselves in the culinary arts, both in urban centers and overseas, where

the demand for their skills is greater. These culinary artists have adapted their carving talents to create intricate designs in ice, fruits and vegetables, transforming food into visual masterpieces. Their creations often grace the buffet tables of cruise ships and luxury hotels and restaurants, showcasing their heritage and artistry on a global stage.

Climate Change Impact on Market Demand

The COVID-19 pandemic has had also a profound impact on market demand of the woodcarvers' products, as revealed by key informants. The COVID 19-pandemic has already shown how external factors can drastically reduce customer flow and demand as they have experienced no customer during that time. The enforced lockdowns led to a drastic reduction in customer footfall, severely affecting sales and income. A similar impact could be expected if climate change leads to more frequent health crises or travel restriction

One interviewee shared a particularly emotional story of having to sell all his chisels, essential tools of for carving, to provide for his family's basic needs. This act underscores the desperation faced by artisans during the pandemic, as they grappled with the uncertainty of its duration and the potential long-term effects on their craft.

As the industry begins to recover and operations gradually return to normalcy, the artisans are now confronted with a new challenge: the rising cost of tools for woodcarving. The scarcity of suppliers has exacerbated this issue, with only one individual in the town reportedly selling various types of chisels. This monopoly has led to a significant increase in prices. The cost of a single chisel has skyrocketed from a mere PHP 7.00 to a range of PHP 150.00 – PHP 300.00. Furthermore, a complete set of chisels, which is indispensable for woodcarving, now costs PHP 12,000.00—a steep price that reflects the economic hardships and inflationary pressures faced by

the woodcarving community in the wake of the pandemic. This could be due to the economic effects of climate change such as inflation. This situation not only affects the artisans' ability to practice their craft but also threatens the preservation of their cultural heritage, as the financial burden may deter new generations from pursuing this traditional art form.

Figure 12. Various type of chisels used for woodcarving by the Paete carvers.

The town sees a surge in demand during Holy Week as devotees flock to acquire religious artifacts, including figures of saints. Traditionally, this period marks a peak in sales for local artisans. According to the Municipal Tourism Officer, Mr. Michael Cadapan, March and April are the busiest months for tourism, with many visitors coming specifically for religious woodcrafts as illustrated in Figure 13. Outside of this peak period, tourist numbers are notably lower. The head chief expressed

concern that a decline in the woodcarving industry could lead to a significant reduction in tourism, which is currently bolstered by the town’s reputation for exquisite religious artistry.

Figure 13. Summary of tourist arrivals from 2013-2023 in Paete, Laguna.

Source: Municipal Tourism Office (See Appendix H).

Innovative Techniques, Materials, and Artistic Processes of Paete

Woodcarvers in Response to Climate Change

Climate change-induced extreme heat has a tangible impact on entire wood carving process, from the selection of raw materials to the application of finishing touches. Such conditions can cause the wood to expand or contract, leading to potential warping or cracking that undermines the precision and integrity of the carvings. According to the Paete artisans, the drying times for finishes are susceptible to weather conditions too; cold weather prolongs the drying, whereas hot, dry conditions can hasten it, resulting in brush marks or an uneven finish.

Environmental shifts can introduce wood defects like checking and splitting, threatening the structural integrity of the carving (Wood Magazine, 2016). For Climate Change and Cultural Heritage: A Qualitative Study of the Paete Wood Carvers in the Philippines...

instance, rainfall patterns determine the moisture levels in carving wood. When rainfall is abundant, it can increase the moisture content of wood, making it more flexible and easier to carve. Artisans, aware of these natural fluctuations, often plan their carving activities around the expected drying times of their materials. They understand that wood with higher moisture content will take longer to dry and adjust their schedules accordingly. Proper drying is essential to prevent the wood from cracking or warping, which can compromise the integrity of the finished piece. Conversely, during periods of low rainfall, wood tends to dry out, becoming harder and more challenging to work with, but hastens the drying.

Tool performance is another aspect affected by extreme temperatures, with tools becoming more brittle in the cold or losing sharpness in the heat, which can hinder the carving process. The work environment itself can become challenging, as uncomfortable conditions may reduce a carver's productivity and the overall quality of work, leading many to prefer working at night when temperatures are cooler.

Additionally, certain wood types, like mango wood, lack of natural resistance to decay and pests, need a chemical treatment to enhance durability. Carvers have turned to these preservation methods, especially for woods of lesser quality compared to Batikuling wood. These preservatives are administered via brushing, spraying, or dipping (Teaca et al, 2019). Humidity changes also play a critical role, as high humidity can cause wood to swell, while low humidity can lead to drying and shrinking, affecting both the carving process and the long-term stability of the wood (Smith, 2016). To mitigate these effects, wood carvers are vigilant and proactive, perhaps by controlling the carving environment, selecting wood species that are more resistant to weather-related stresses, and adjusting their techniques and materials to better suit the prevailing conditions, ensuring the artistry and durability of their work.

Technology and Adoption Techniques

The transition from traditional tools to modern technology in Paete wood carving represents a significant evolution in the craft. The 'kinstay' or chisel, was once the primary tool for shaping and carving wood. However, the introduction of power saws and other electric tools has revolutionized the process. These modern tools allow artisans to make more precise cuts, work faster, and handle larger volumes of work with greater efficiency. This shift not only saves time but also reduces the physical strain on the carvers, enabling them to focus on the finer details of their art. One example is Jose Maralita, aged 47, with 30 years of experience in woodcarving. He utilizes electric tools to cut woods and create a large number of symbolic item, particularly the carabao, for the Boy Scout of the Philippines (Figure 14).

Figure 14. Woodcarving process using electric tools.

In terms of design, Paete carvers have traditionally relied on their imagination and hand-drawn sketches to plan their works. Today, they are increasingly adopting computer layout drawing. This modern approach allows for meticulous planning and the ability to visualize the final product before the carving process begins. By using software, carvers can experiment with designs, make adjustments,

and ensure accuracy, which is particularly beneficial for complex or large-scale projects. This blend of traditional craftsmanship with contemporary techniques ensures that the rich heritage of Paete wood carving continues to thrive in the modern era.

By embracing these materials, Paete artisans are not only keeping their traditional skills alive but also expanding their knowledge. This versatility opens up new markets and opportunities for them.

Innovative Materials

In the face of wood scarcity, many artisans have adapted by incorporating resin into their craft-making. Resin, a versatile and readily available material, streamlines the production process, enabling the creation of products on a larger scale with less complexity compared to traditional wood carving. However, resin can pose health hazards due to its chemical content such as Bisphenol-A Diglycidyl Ether (BADGE), which can harm the respiratory system of individuals with prolonged exposure (Demeterio III, 2024). This adaptation, while innovative, carries considerable consequences for the community of traditional woodcarvers. As the market begins to favor resin-based crafts due to their cost-effectiveness and ease of production, the demand for the intricate skills of woodcarvers diminishes. This shift can lead to a significant reduction in employment opportunities for these craftsmen, as their specialized abilities become less sought after in a market evolving towards modern materials. The resulting job displacement poses a threat to the livelihood of woodcarvers, leaving many without work and facing dwindling chances to engage customers who now opt for the alternative resin products. This trend not only impacts individual artisans but also has the potential to erode the cultural heritage associated with traditional woodcraft, as the artistry and techniques honed over generations may

see a decline in transmission and practice.

Somehow, with changing times and availability of new materials, these skilled craftsmen of Paete have expanded their repertoire. They are now exploring and mastering the use of alternative materials such as Styrofoam, plaster of Paris, and paper Mache (Figure 15). This diversification not only showcases their ability to adapt and learn but also allows them to express their artistry in new and varied forms.

Figure 15. Innovative crafts by Paete artisan using new materials.

Source: (Left) Craft is made from Paper Mache and was captured from mini-gallery of Municipal Tourism Office, Paete Laguna. (Right) Religious items are made from resin and was captured from Galaboc Shop.

The use of styrofoam, for instance, offers a lightweight and easily moldable medium that can be carved with precision analogous to wood. Plaster of Paris, on the other hand, sets into a hard, durable form, allowing the creation of more permanent structures. Paper mâché is a versatile art form that involves creating objects from paper pieces or pulp, bound with an adhesive paste (Demeterio III, 2024). In essence,

the Paete artisans' willingness to innovate and their skillful adoption of new materials are testament to their enduring artistry and the vibrant culture of craftsmanship in their town in facing the greatest challenge in wood supply.

The Resilience of Paete Community on Wood Carving Industry

Adaptive Strategies

The situation in Paete woodcarving heritage is a complex interplay of environmental, economic, and cultural factors. The scarcity of wood supply, which is attributed to climate change and the enforcement of total log bans in the Philippines, prompted proactive measures from the community and local leaders.

In these challenging times, one of the great master carvers in the town, Justin “Paloy” Cagayat, Jr. began cultivating Batikuling trees on his land back in 2010. This foresighted action represents a long-term investment for the future of the industry. His commitment extends beyond personal gain; he aims to ensure that the intricate art of woodcarving continues for generations to come (Sagcal, 2023).

Through initiatives like this, artisans like Paloy contribute significantly to the town's identity as the Carving Capital of the Philippines. His resilience and passion serve as a beacon of hope, even during challenging times when customer interest wanes. By nurturing their craft and planting the seeds—both literally and symbolically—for the next generation, they sustain a legacy that transcends mere wood and chisels.

In response also to this crisis, former Mayor Rogilyn Bagabaldo took proactive measures by initiating the construction of an access road to facilitate the planting of Batikuling trees in upland area. This effort was aimed at replenishing the wood supply essential for the artisans. The initiative was further supported by a permaculture

upland agro-reforestation program, enabling woodcarvers to grow woodcraft trees on their own properties, thus fostering a sustainable source of materials for their craft (Sagcal, 2023).

In 2018, a significant milestone was achieved through a partnership with Southern Luzon State University, resulting in the planting of around 4,000 Batikuling trees in Gumihan Park (Gutierrez, 2020). However, maintaining the park has proven to be a challenge, with overgrowth and neglect diminishing its aesthetics and functionality as it became eventually an agri-ecotourism destination for other universities (Sagcal, 2023).

The subsequent administration under Mayor Ronald Cosico is also committed to the growth of Batikuling trees. However, Gumihan Park land's temporary usufruct rights, which are set to expire after 10 years, could affect the project's future benefits. His proposal is to purchase the land by the government to ensure the security of the Batikuling trees and, by extension, the wood carving industry. This vision can extend beyond mere conservation but a community-driven approach where families will become the caretakers of the forest. Yet, up to this date, the Municipal Planning & Development Office chief, confirmed that it is still under negotiation.

The local administration of Paete is also employing tourism as a strategic avenue to preserve and promote their cultural heritage of woodcarving. The plan, as outlined by the Tourism Office chief, includes establishing a museum dedicated to the town's master carvers. This initiative aims to offer tourists a deeper understanding of the woodcrafts, beyond just purchasing products, by showcasing the artisans' artworks.

Currently, the municipal tourism office collaborates with two private museums: Museo Ac-Ac and Ash Gallery & Café. The Museo Ac-Ac, charging an entrance fee of

PHP 150.00, exhibits the works of Master Sculptor Luisito B. Ac-Ac, who is celebrated for his depictions of Philippine folklore, children at play, religious imagery, and anatomical masterpieces. The Ac-Ac family also runs one of the largest woodcraft industries in Paete.

Figure 16. The Museo Ac-ac in Paete, Laguna.

Source: Google Photos

On the other hand, Ash Gallery & Café (Figure 17) operates as a non-profit entity under the Paete Science and Business College Inc. It offers free educational visits and tours, highlighting the art of both established and emerging local artists, including students. At the Ash Gallery & Café, visitors can enjoy a variety of refreshments and tasty cuisine amidst an array of unique woodcrafts.

Figure 17. The Ash Gallery & Café in Paete, Laguna.

The Paete Festival serves as another platform for artisans to showcase their skills through a carving competition with various categories based on different mediums such as fruits, vegetables, soap, and clay. Figure 18 features the clay art created by the winners of the carving competition during the Paete Festivals. It showcases the talent of young Paete artisans in different medium, the clay.

Figure 18. Clay art made by a young Paete artisans.

Source: Captured from the mini-gallery of Municipal Tourism Office, Paete Laguna

Furthermore, to ensure the longevity of their woodcarving legacy, the local government has considered integrating carving into vocational training through Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA). Although initially proposed as a school curriculum, yet it should pass several processes. However, the idea evolved into offering carving as a vocational course, recognizing that many Paete artists have gained international acclaim.

Resilience of the Woodcarving Industry Among Younger Generation

A focus group discussion with local youth revealed a significant gap in awareness regarding the impact of climate change on the woodcarving industry. The

responses from the younger generation indicate that they have limited awareness of climate change's impact on their traditional craft and possess limited experience in woodcarving (Figure 24).

Despite their lineage of skilled carvers, there is a noticeable reluctance to seek guidance from elders in mastering the craft. This change is attributed to the influence of contemporary society, where sports and social media captivate the youth's attention, leading them away from the meticulous art of woodcarving.

For most of the youth, their exposure to carving is primarily theoretical, limited to academic projects. Their education in the craft involves using more softer materials such as soap and vegetables, rather than traditional wood. This, coupled with the scarcity of wood, has prompted a transition to alternative teaching materials, which unintentionally distances the young from the conventional woodcarving art form.

This disinterest of the youths on wood carving is partly due to the perceived lack of income and recognition associated with the craft. Many youths are opting for alternative careers due to the limited financial prospects in the woodcarving industry. Currently, the trend of carving with ice, fruits, and vegetables is on the rise, capturing the attention of the younger generation. Consequently, even established and talented carvers from Paete are relocating abroad, following in the footsteps of their predecessors, in pursuit of more rewarding opportunities.

However, there is a silver lining. The youth have not completely dismissed the possibility of pursuing woodcarving as a future career. They recognize their potential role in preserving their cultural heritage for future generations. To foster this interest, they propose that local government support through free training and workshops could revitalize youth engagement in woodcarving. Although carving competitions exist, participation is limited due to the lack of practical experience among the youth,

particularly in woodcarving.

Resilience of the Woodcarving Industry Among the Local Government of Paete

The local government of Paete is at a critical stage, striving to uphold the sustainability of the traditional woodcarving industry amidst environmental and societal challenges. With a budget that falls short of the needs, their efforts to implement comprehensive sustainable forest management and other crucial mitigation strategies are significantly hampered. The quest to obtain an exemption from the Philippines' total log ban, which would have been a help in maintaining a steady wood supply for the carvers, unfortunately, did not come to execution.

Despite these setbacks, proactive measures are being taken. Reforestation projects in the highlands are underway, aiming to reverse the trend of depleting wood resources. These green initiatives not only promise a future for woodcarving but also contribute to ecological balance.

Furthermore, the local government is turning to tourism as a powerful tool to reinforce the woodcarving industry. By promoting and celebrating Paete's woodcarving heritage, they hope to attract visitors and enthusiasts from around the globe. This strategy is not just about economic gain, it is a cultural movement to strengthen pride in the local craft and inspire a new generation of carvers.

Resilience of the Woodcarving Industry Among the Artisans of Paete

On a more positive note, the skilled artisans of Paete are so devoted to their craft that they continue to carve and showcase their work in their shops, even when there are no immediate buyers. They persist in their artistry with the hope that eventually, someone will appreciate and purchase their creations. The artisans acknowledge that the effects of climate change could worsen in the coming years, but they remain steadfast in their commitment to their craft. As one of the interviewees

says, “*Hanggang may uukitin, hindi kami titigil sa pag-ukit* (As long as there is something to carve, we will not stop carving)” (E. Afuang, personal communication, 2024, April 10).

They may not be able to compel their children to follow in their footsteps, but they refuse to abandon their culture because it is their identity and the means by which they have supported their families. This optimistic outlook is a commendable trait among the Paete artisans, helping to sustain their legacy and preserve their rich cultural heritage.

XI. RECOMMENDATION AND CONCLUSION

The Paete woodcarving industry is grappling with the impact of climate change, which has led to a scarcity of wood supply due to extreme weather events and wildfires causing deforestation. This scarcity has driven up the cost of materials, placing a financial strain on the carvers of Paete. The pandemic further exacerbated the situation, leading to decreased sales and impacting the livelihoods of artisans and the overall demand within the industry. Despite these challenges, the community's innovative spirit and the support from local authorities, through initiatives like planting Batikuling seeds and enhancing tourism, demonstrate a strong commitment to preserving this age-old art for future.

Engaging the youth is vital for the continuation of Paete's cultural legacy. It is essential to cultivate attractive opportunities and nurturing environments that inspire young people to take up this noble craft. A concerted effort from the community, local government, and educational institutions is necessary to captivate the younger generation and secure the art form's survival. Continuous education and skill enhancement for carvers to master the art of traditional wood carving are crucial. Utilizing digital platforms to display the exquisite skills of Paete's carvers through motivational videos can also play a significant role in this endeavor. The community-driven initiatives to promote local crafts, leveraging digital marketing and e-commerce to reach wider audiences, and forming partnerships with interior designers and hospitality businesses to integrate Paete's wood carvings into contemporary settings can be adapted to continue to thrive for the wood carving industry.

In light of the dwindling supply of the preferred Batikuling wood, it is imperative to conduct comprehensive research into the conservation and potential of Paraiso (*Melia azedarach* L.) and Yamane (*Gmelina arborea* Roxb. ex Sm.) trees. These

species have been identified by the Department of Science and Technology's Forest Products Research and Development Institute (DOST FPRDI) as having comparable properties to Batikuling, offering a promising alternative to address the raw material shortages afflicting the woodcarving industry.

The Paete woodcarving community stands at a crossroads where environmental, economic, and generational challenges intersect. By uniting efforts and embracing innovative and sustainable practices, they can overcome these challenges and continue to flourish, ensuring that their rich cultural heritage is preserved and remains vibrant for future generations.

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Appendices

APPENDIX A

Approved Interview Request Letter

This section includes the approved interview request letter with the Municipal Mayor of Paete, Laguna and municipal offices.

Figure 19. Interview request letter to the Municipal Mayor of Paete, Laguna.

interview at your earliest convenience. I am flexible with the date and time, and I can adjust to your schedule.

Please feel free to contact me via email ma.jameladimapilis@gmail.com or phone **0906-024-5054** to arrange a suitable time for the interview. I appreciate your consideration and look forward to hearing from you.

Thank you for your time and support in advancing our understanding of the intersection between climate change and cultural heritage. Your cooperation in this academic endeavor would be greatly appreciated.

Sincerely,

Ma. Jamela V. Dimapilis
Graduate Student
Faculty of Management and Development
University of the Philippines-Open University

APPENDIX B

Interview Schedule

This section comprises the form utilized to collect the socio-demographic profile of the participants and the interview questions guide.

Figure 20. Interview Questions Guide

Socio-Economic Profile				
Name (<i>Pangalan</i>):				
Address (<i>Tirahan</i>):				
Age (<i>Edad</i>):	<input type="checkbox"/>	18 and below	<input type="checkbox"/>	41-50
	<input type="checkbox"/>	19-30	<input type="checkbox"/>	51-60
	<input type="checkbox"/>	31-40	<input type="checkbox"/>	61 and above
Gender (<i>Kasarian</i>):	<input type="checkbox"/>	Male (<i>Lalaki</i>)	<input type="checkbox"/>	Female (<i>Babae</i>)
Level of Education (<i>Antas ng Edukasyon</i>):		No formal education (<i>Walang pormal na edukasyon</i>)		Tertiary level Graduate (<i>Nagtapos ng Kolehiyo</i>)
		Primary level graduate (<i>Nagtapos ng primarya/elementarya</i>)		Master Degree Graduate (<i>Nagtapos ng Master Degree</i>)
		Secondary level graduate (<i>Nagtapos ng sekundarya</i>)		Doctorate Degree Graduate (<i>Nagtapos ng Doctorate Degree</i>)
Occupation (<i>Trabaho</i>):				
Years of Experience in Wood Carving Industry (<i>Taon ng Karanasan sa Industriya ng Pag-ukit ng Kahoy</i>)				
No. of household members (<i>Bilang ng Kasapi ng Pamilya</i>)	<input type="checkbox"/>	5 and below		
	<input type="checkbox"/>	6-10		
	<input type="checkbox"/>	11 and above		
Average household's monthly income: (<i>Buwanang kita ng Pamilya</i>)		10,000 and below	<input type="checkbox"/>	40,100 – 50,000
		10,100 – 20,000	<input type="checkbox"/>	50,100 – 60,000
		20,100 – 30,000	<input type="checkbox"/>	60,100 – 70,000
		30,100 – 40,000	<input type="checkbox"/>	70,100 and above
Community Role: (<i>Tungkulin sa Lipunan</i>)		Local official (<i>Opisyal ng local na pamahalaan</i>)	<input type="checkbox"/>	Businessman (<i>Negosyante</i>)
		Non-government officials (<i>Mga opisyal ng organisasyong di-pampamahalaan</i>)	<input type="checkbox"/>	Skilled Worker (<i>Mangagawa</i>)
		Religious Leader (<i>Pinuno ng Pang-relihiyosong samahan</i>)	<input type="checkbox"/>	Others (<i>Iba pa</i>)

Interview Schedule

Focus Area	Example of Questions
<p>Knowledge and Perception about Climate Change (<i>Kaalaman at Pananaw sa Pagbabago ng Klima</i>)</p>	<p>How knowledgeable are you about the issues of climate change? (<i>Gaano kayo kaalam sa mga isyu ng pagbabago ng klima?</i>)</p> <p>What specific challenges or threats related to climate change do the wood carvers in Paete face? (<i>Anong tiyak na hamon o banta na may kaugnayan sa pagbabago ng klima ang kinakaharap ng mga mang-uukit sa Paete?</i>)</p> <p>Can you describe how climate change has affected the wood carving industry in Paete? (<i>Maari mo bang ilarawan kung paano naapektuhan ng pagbabago ng klima ang industriya ng pag-ukit ng kahoy sa Paete?</i>)</p> <p>What is your perspective on the impact of climate change on the wood carving industry? (<i>Ano ang iyong pananaw sa epekto ng pagbabago ng klima sa industriya ng pag-ukit ng kahoy?</i>)</p> <p>How does climate change affect your traditional knowledge and skills in wood carving? (<i>Paano nakakaapekto ang pagbabago ng klima sa inyong tadisyon na kaalaman at kasanayan sa pag-ukit ng kahoy?</i>)</p>
<p>Economic Impact of Climate Change (<i>Epekto sa Ekonomiya ng Pagbabago ng Klima</i>)</p>	<p>Have you noticed any changes in the demand for Paete wood carvings due to climate change? (<i>Napansin mo ba ang anumang pagbabago sa pangangailangan para sa mga ukit na kahoy mula sa Paete dahil sa pagbabago ng klima?</i>)</p> <p>How has climate change impacted the economic sustainability of your carving business? (<i>Paano nakakaapekto ang pagbabago ng klima sa pang-ekonomiyang katatagan ng iyong negosyo sa pag-ukit?</i>)</p> <p>Can you share any experiences where weather events directly affected your livelihood? (<i>Maari mo bang ibahagi ang anumang karanasan kung saan direktang naapektuhan ng mga pangyayari sa panahon ang iyong kabuhayan?</i>)</p>

<p>Adoption of Innovations (<i>Adaptasyon at Pagbabago</i>)</p>	<p>What innovative techniques or materials have you adopted in response to changing climatic conditions? (<i>Anong mga makabagong teknik o materyales ang inyong ginamit bilang tugon sa nagbabagong kondisyon ng klima?</i>)</p> <p>How do you balance maintaining traditional artistic processes with the need to adapt to climate change? (<i>Paano ninyo pinapanatili ang tradisyonal na proseso ng artistikong pag-uukit habang inaangkop ito sa pagbabago ng klima?</i>)</p> <p>Are there any new designs or products you have created because of environmental changes? (<i>Mayroon ba kayong nilikhang mga bagong disenyo o produkto bunga ng mga pagbabago sa kapaligiran?</i>)</p>
<p>Community Resilience (<i>Katatagan ng Komunidad</i>)</p>	<p>What strategies has the Paete wood carving community implemented to cope with climate-related challenges? (<i>Anong mga estratehiya ang ipinatupad ng komunidad ng mga mag-uukit sa Paete para makayanan ang mga hamong may kinalaman sa pagbabago ng klima?</i>)</p> <p>How do you preserve your cultural identity and heritage while adapting to climate change? (<i>Paano ninyo pinapanatili ang inyong pagkakakilanlang kultural at pamana habang inaangkop ang sarili sa pagbabago ng klima?</i>)</p> <p>In your opinion, what makes the Paete wood carving community resilient in the face of climate change? (<i>Sa iyong palagay, ano ang nagpapatatag sa komunidad ng mga mag-uukit sa Paete sa harap ng pagbabago ng klima?</i>)</p> <p>What recommendations do the wood carvers have for policymakers and stakeholders to address climate change impacts on their craft? (<i>Ano ang mga rekomendasyon ng mga mang-uukit para sa mga gumagawa ng patakaran at mga stakeholder upang tugunan ang epekto ng pagbabago ng klima sa kanilang sining?</i>)</p>

APPENDIX C

Interview and Focus Group Discussions

This section provides the summary of the socio-demographic profile of the participants and includes photos from the interview and focus group discussions.

Figure 21. Profile of the interviewees.

Code	Name	Age	Gender	Marital Status	Level of Education	Community Role	Years of Experience in Wood Carving	Monthly Income
1	Emil Afuang	52	Male	Married	Secondary Level Graduate	Skilled Worker	30	12,000
2	Nestor Daguitan	58	Male	Married	Secondary Level Undergraduate	Skilled Worker	30	12,000
3	Jose Maralita	47	Male	Married	Secondary Level Graduate	Skilled Worker	30	20,000
4	Zaldy Coronel	63	Male	Married	Secondary Level Undergraduate	Skilled Worker	50	9,000
5	Nasario Galaboc, Jr.	53	Male	Single	Secondary Level Graduate	Business Owner	33	50,000
6	Alfredo Afuang	55	Male	Married	Secondary Level Graduate	Skilled Worker	20	10,000
7	Peds Madrigal	51	Male	Married	Tertiary Level Graduate	Business Owner	27	25,000
8	Amador Dimatatak	45	Male	Single	Secondary Level Graduate	Skilled Worker	20	12,000
9	Arnold Jimena	42	Male	Single	Primary Level Graduate	Skilled Worker	9	3,000
10	Edmund Lanuza	45	Male	Married	Secondary Level Graduate	Skilled Worker	30	16,000
11	Michael Cadapan	43	Male	Single	Tertiary Level Graduate	Government Employee	0	25,000
12	Ma. Nancy Cagayan	40	Female	Married	Tertiary Level Graduate	Government Employee	0	25,000
13	Jeriel Baldemor	27	Male	Married	Tertiary Level Graduate	Government Employee	0	25,000
14	Albert Noceja	49	Male	Married	Tertiary Level Graduate	Government Employee	0	25,000

Figure 22. Photos from the interview.

Note: Emil Afuang, a Paete artisan, known for his craftsmanship and effort that goes into creating intricate design and unique doors, called as '*labor*'.

Note: Nazario Galaboc, Jr., a Paete artisan and the proprietor of Galaboc Shop, small-scale woodcarving workshop in Paete, Laguna.

Note: An interview with the Municipal Disaster Risk and Reduction Management

Head Chief, Mr. Albert Noceja, took place on April 16, 2024.

Figure 23. Photos from the focus group discussions.

Note: A focus group discussion participated by the residents of Paete, Laguna, took place on April 10, 2024.

Note: A focus group discussion participated by the young people of Paete, Laguna, took place on May 19, 2024.

Figure 24. Profile and responses from the focus group discussion with Paete's youth

FOCUS GROUP DISCUSSION AMONG YOUNGER GENERATION OF PAETE
MAY 19, 2024

PANGALAN	KASARIAN	EDAD	KNOWLEDGEABLE ABOUT IMPACT OF CLIMATE CHANGE ON WOODCARVING (YES/NO)	WITH PRACTICAL EXPERIENCE OF WOOD CARVING (YES/NO)
1. Kyle Olac	Lalake	19		
2. Alvien Bagacina	Lalake	14	NO	NO
3. Vito Alvarez	Lalake	18	NO	NO
4. Johan Oclarit	Lalake	20	NO	NO
5. Gilbert Oliver Jr.	Lalake	21	NO	YES
6. Julian Mc Clyde A. Afuang	Lalake	13	NO	NO
7. Princess Nicole Atuang	Lalake	13	NO	NO
8. Guillermo F. Oliver III	Lalake	21	NO	NO
9. PERNIS PARDOS	MACE	26	NO	YES
10. Charles Laruga	Male	21	NO	NO
11. MARK JORDAN MERRAL	Male	17	NO	NO
12. PERLA JANELLA B. JAVILINA	Female	19	NO	YES
13. Lovely Jean Samientos	Female	18	NO	NO

Note. The responses from the younger generation indicate that they have limited awareness of climate change's impact on their traditional craft and possess limited experience in woodcarving.

APPENDIX D

Transcribed Interview

This section contains the transcribed audio recording of the interview with the participants.

Figure 25. Transcription of the interview with the participant.

Interviewee: Zaldy Coronel

Date: April 10, 2024

[Speaker 1]

So, pwede po makuha ang pangalan po ni sir? Zaldi Coronel Dito na po sa Paete po kayo nagtira?

[Speaker 2]

Oo, dito. Ay, 63 years old na ako eh.

[Speaker 1]

63?

[Speaker 2]

Siyam na taon na akong dumating dito. Lahing Bicolano ako eh.

[Speaker 1]

Ah, 9 years old po kayo dito. Dahil po, paano kayo napunta dito?

[Speaker 2]

Dahil dito pala pupunta mag-uukit.

[Speaker 1]

Kung baga dito pala inyong destiny.

[Speaker 2]

Dito pala ako magkakaasawa pa rin.

[Speaker 1]

Sino po nagdala sa inyo po dito nung kaisyam na taon?

[Speaker 2]

Eh, po ang kapatid ko.

[Speaker 1]

Ah, kapatid nyo lang po. Pero po ang mother and father niya po naiwan sa Bicol?

[Speaker 2]

Hindi po, nandito din ng halipin.

[Speaker 1]

Nandito na. Nandito na rin po. So, ano po yung pinakamataas na edukasyon na natapos po natin?

[Speaker 2]

Ako? Ayun. Background lang ng first year eh.

[Speaker 1]

First year.

[Speaker 2]

Natuto na ako ng magkalukuhan. Hindi na ako nagtuloy (mag-aral).

[Speaker 1]

First year. High school po?

[Speaker 2]

College? Hindi. High school.

Hindi ko tinuloy yun.

[Speaker 1]

So, ito pong trabaho nyo po ay skilled worker? O kayo po e may-ari? Ay ano lang?

Kayo po ang may negosyo? Kayo po yung nakikipag-usap sa mga customer?

[Speaker 2]

Natanggap lang ako. Pupunta dito, ukitin mo ito, o sige.

[Speaker 1]

So, parang inuusap po kayo, sila ang talaga may kliyente?

[Speaker 2]

Bibigyan nila ako ng... Ilang araw mo gagawin yan? Lalayo ko naman ng kunti.

Sige, sige, ganitong araw.

[Speaker 1]

Ilang taon na po kayo sa karanasan sa wood carving?

[Speaker 2]

Matagal na. Kung 9 years old po ako (nagsimula)? Panahon pa ng kutsara yun, nagaganito na ako.

[Speaker 1]
Kutsara ang gamit po?

[Speaker 2]
Ano yung kutsara yun? Old decor yun?
Mga kutsara ang kutsara.

[Speaker 1]
Malalaki. Mga ilang taon po? 30, 40?

[Speaker 2]
Bata pa yun eh. Inuupahan lang ako ng tinapay. Anohin mo yan?

Sige, o. Ayusin mo yan. Bibigyan lang ako.

[Speaker 1]
Mga 50 years po?

[Speaker 2]
63 na eh. 54 na yun. Hanggang ngayon.

May uban na nga po.

[Speaker 1]
Magaling pa rin namang magukit. Ilan po kayong, may mga anak po kayo?

[Speaker 2]
Dalawa lalaki. Isang may asawa, may anak ng tatlo. Yung isa binata po, nagtatrabaho sa pagsanjan.

[Speaker 1]
Si misis po.

[Speaker 2]
Ando, nangipaglibig. May patay kami yung kuya namin. Hindi nga ako sumama, naglinis ako dyan.

[Speaker 1]
Magkano naman po yung buwan ang kita nyo sa paguukit?

[Speaker 2]
Minsan pag sinipag, limandaan. Sa isang buwan po.

[Speaker 1]

Average lang po.

[Speaker 2]
Liitan na lang, gawin natin tatlong daan, isang araw.

[Speaker 1]
Sa isang araw po, 300.

[Speaker 2]
Liitan natin. Baka mamay sabihing malaking kinikita ng tao dito.

[Speaker 1]
Malaki palang kinikita doon. Meron ba po kayo ibang trabaho bukod po sa paguukit?

[Speaker 2]
Ayun naman. Carpentero. Mason.

Kaya lang, ayaw ko na noon, napakainit. Hindi na kaya ng katawan po. Noon po, nag-aano pa po kayo?

[Speaker 1]
Sideline, construction.

[Speaker 2]
Pag tinatamad ako nito, yun ang gagawin ko. Mabilis pati ako gumawa.

[Speaker 1]
Tapos, magpapasok naman po kayo sa ibang trabaho. Kayo po ay manggagawa.

[Speaker 2]
Manggagawa talaga.

[Speaker 1]
Okay, next po. Ito na po yung may relation sa climate change na matanong ko.

[Speaker 2]
Sasagutin ko nang sasagutin.

[Speaker 1]
Sa 1 to 10 po. May examination na eh. Sa 1 to 10 po, gaano niyo po kaalamang yung mga issue sa climate change?

10 po ang pinakamataas.

[Speaker 2]
Pinakamataas. Eh, gawin natin. Eh, parang syempre may mali eh.

Ibawasan natin, 9.

[Speaker 1]
So ano naman po yung mga nakikitan yung naging pagbabago ng klima po dito? Katulad ng pag-init.

[Speaker 2]
Ay, oo nga yan. Sasabihin.

[Speaker 1]
Kasi po diba 50 years halos na kayong naggaganyan? Noon po ba ganito na rin katindi ang init?

[Speaker 2]
Ay hindi. Kung mo nga maedad na ano, paglalabas ng ganitong panahon, masakit sa ulo. Tapos biglang aambun, napakainit.

Iba ng panahon.

[Speaker 1]
Iba ang panahon.

[Speaker 2]
Pag humapon naman na, may malamig. Ano nung? Malamig sa hapon ah.

Kaya dapat may papainit.

[Speaker 1]
All in practice. Dila nagpapainit.

[Speaker 2]
Ayit na, ang bawal na nga.

[Speaker 1]
Yung pong mga ganyong ano, yan pong, klima, changes ng klima, nakakapegto po sa paggawa niyo? Sa tingin niyo po?

[Speaker 2]
Nakakapekto, ma'am.

[Speaker 1]
Minsan po.

[Speaker 2]
Alam niyo kung bakit? Bakit po? Ay, mainit.

[Speaker 1]
Opo. So kapag po, ano pong oras na lang kayong gumagawa? Ang ganda po, kainit.

Gagawa po kayo o magpapaliban na lang po.

[Speaker 2]
Minsan, pag napaka-rush, ano? Pag-rush. Ukit na lang akong lalagyan po ng electric fan.

[Speaker 1]
Electric fan. Pero kapag po, hindi naman po nagmamadali.

[Speaker 2]
Anjan ako sa mga ilalim ng puno.

[Speaker 1]
Mga anong oras po kayong nag-uukit?

[Speaker 2]
Gabi-gabi.

[Speaker 1]
Gabi na lang? Kasi mas malamig.

[Speaker 2]
Mga tatlong oras, hapa.

[Speaker 1]
Ah, 3 to 4 hours yung per day niyo po nang-uukit. Ano po yun, yung task ko? Continue na lang po next ano?

[Speaker 2]
Pag umaga, yan. Hindi pa mainit.

[Speaker 1]
Next day, ganyan po. So, ito. Ay, paano naman po nakakapekto yung ito nga pong

climate change sa inyong traditional na kaalaman at kasanayan?

Yung pong mga knowledge niyo po?

[Speaker 2]
Hindi, katulad nga po ng... Di ba madaling pupuntahan mo? Di ka makapunta, napakainit nga.

Yung papupuntahin ka ng personal, mamaya na, ang init eh. Minsan, maambun eh. So, hindi na po minsan pinutuloy muna?

Dito sa paitiga niya, sabi, napakainit. Mamaya, may ambun niya.

[Speaker 1]
May ambun na?

[Speaker 2]
Oo.

[Speaker 1]
Kapag po bagyo po kaya dito, malakas din po magbagyo dito?

[Speaker 2]
Hindi naman, gawaan nitong Sierra Madre. Sa taas, napakalakas ng hangin dyan, sumisipol dyan.

[Speaker 1]
Hangin lang po pagka may bagyo.

[Speaker 2]
Maririnig mo lang yun.

[Speaker 1]
Ah, dito po yung Sierra Madre na?

[Speaker 2]
Ayan na.

[Speaker 1]
Ah, talaga po.

[Speaker 2]
Ang haba.

[Speaker 1]
Ang baha, wala naman po kayo na experience na pagbaha.

[Speaker 2]
Ah, meron. Abot dito, dyan. May tilapia nga dyan eh.

[Speaker 1]
May tilapia.

[Speaker 2]
Mga ganito kalalaking lalaro sila.

[Speaker 1]
Pagbaha po, ganun din. Kasi, paano, bakit po kaya wala nang mga puno dun sa taas?

[Speaker 2]
Ay siya, ay puno nga. Sa halip na yung ilog ay iisa, dadalawa yung dadaanan. Pinagpuputol dito, dumaan na kung saan-saan.

Malakas ang tubig eh.

[Speaker 1]
Malakas yan.

[Speaker 2]
Dala-dala nyan, maski bato. Pagdumaan yan.

[Speaker 1]
Noong pong araw, noong pong kayo po, mga younger age niyo po, hindi po gano'ng kagrabe.

[Speaker 2]
Hindi. Walang ganun.

[Speaker 1]
Ah, wala. Walang ganun. Ngayon lang po, dito na lang po.

[Speaker 2]
Ngayon na lang. Wala nang pinuputol na nga ng gusto.

[Speaker 1]
Wala na.

[Speaker 2]
Mga tao, mga puno.

[Speaker 1]
Ito naman po, dadaako naman po tayo sa epekto sa ekonomiya po. Napansin niyo po ba na mayroong pagbabago sa mga pangangailangan o gamit na kailangan nyo sa paguukit ng kakoy dahil sa pagbabago ng klima. So nagbago po po yung supplies.

[Speaker 2]
Nagmahal ang bilihin.

[Speaker 1]
Nagmahal ang bilihin.

[Speaker 2]
Mahal yung mga materyalis. Maski yung panguukit, mahal na rin ba?

[Speaker 1]
Yung pong pangganan.

[Speaker 2]
Yung chisel, oo.

[Speaker 1]
Chisel. Mahal ng material.

[Speaker 2]
Dati 17 piso, ngayon ay 300.

[Speaker 1]
Ah, 17 lang po per piece.

[Speaker 2]
Pataas na yun. Yung pinakamali, 300.

[Speaker 1]
So nag-start po kayo 17 pesos lang per piece.

[Speaker 2]
May 7 piso pa nga.

[Speaker 1]

May 7 piso pa po. Yung paunahan nyo pong gawa, 7 piso pa po. Sa kakoy naman po.

[Speaker 2]
Nakoy, mura din noon. Napaka-mura din noon. Parang 150 lang ang bob tip (board foot), no?

Ay, ngayon.

[Speaker 1]
Paano na po ang tawag doon? 150 per ano po?

[Speaker 2]
Board feet.

[Speaker 1]
Board feet? Ah, yun ang sinasabi. Ngayon po, depende sa uri ng kahoy.

[Speaker 2]
Uri ng kahoy, oo. Yung kamagong, yung nagamahal, yan.

[Speaker 1]
Pero po may nagsusupply sa inyo? Kamagong, baka na...

[Speaker 2]
Parang wala na kasi binan (banned) na lang. Mga santol na ngayon, kaya nga napapaknut yung Sierra Madre. Nakawala yung mga tunog.

Kaya kung saan-saan na lumulusot ang tubig, yan. Pababa dito.

[Speaker 1]
Familiar po kayo sa batikuling?

[Speaker 2]
Oo.

[Speaker 1]
Ngayon po, may mga supply pa po ng batikuling kayo?

[Speaker 2]

Oo, meron. Doon yun sa May Queson na, malapit na sa dagat.

[Speaker 1]
Dinadala po dito. Dinadala po dito?

[Speaker 2]
Oo. Diyan sa mga ano. Ang haba pa nga, malalaki.

[Speaker 1]
Halimbawa po, may nagpunta po dito nagpapaukit ako ng ganito. Sino po nagdadala ng kahoy?

[Speaker 2]
Yung mayari.

[Speaker 1]
Ah, dala na rin niya ang kahoy?

[Speaker 2]
Dala na.

[Speaker 1]
As in po, kayo talagang gagawa lang.

[Speaker 2]
Yung kapatid ko, ganyan eh. Yung isa niya, sumama lang paglibig sa kapatid namin. Ako hindi, naghinis ako doon.

[Speaker 1]
Naglinis na po kayo. Noong panahon po ng pandemya, pandemic po, paano po kayo naka... Kasi kung ito po ang kinikita nyo, paano naman po kayo noong pandemya?

[Speaker 2]
Naka ano?

[Speaker 1]
Naka survive.

[Speaker 2]
Ay, may na po ako kahit marami.

[Speaker 1]

Ah, meron din po. So, hindi po kayo nasiro (zero) noong pandemic?

[Speaker 2]
Ah, ganito kalalapad.

[Speaker 1]
Ano po yung...

[Speaker 2]
Religious items yun, all day po.

[Speaker 1]
So, hindi rin naman po kayo nasiro noong pandemic, talagang meron po.

[Speaker 2]
Bawal lumabas eh.

[Speaker 1]
Bawal po.

[Speaker 2]
Pinuntahan yung kapatid po, pinagawa ng yung ano, 4,000 isang piraso.

[Speaker 1]
O, ganay. Buti po may...

[Speaker 2]
May ginagawa, bawal lumabas. Sinusundo naman dito, mayaman naman siya, may sasakyan siya eh.

[Speaker 1]
Pero po, noong mga unang panahon po ninyo, talagang marami po talagang pagawa.

[Speaker 2]
Oo, napakarami. Bawat bahay no. May naguukit dito, tutunog-tunog.

May nagtutok-tok, magkatrabaho yun.

[Speaker 1]
Bawat bahay yun. Ah, talagang kinig. Talagang kinig po yung pagtok-tok.

[Speaker 2]

Bawat bahay yun dito sa Paete no.

[Speaker 1]

Ba't po kayang ngayon, Kaunti na daw po?

[Speaker 2]

Isa pa yung dahilang gawa ng mga gadgets, yun, filter. Tinamad na yung mga bata mag-aral ng mga ganito. Wala nang gustong matuto nitong magukit.

Wala na.

[Speaker 1]

Sa inyo pong pamilya, wala pong mga anak?

[Speaker 2]

Wala.

[Speaker 1]

Wala pong magmamanana sa inyong anak?

[Speaker 2]

Ay, dadalawa naman yung anak po, walang hilig.

[Speaker 1]

Walang hilig.

[Speaker 2]

Wala. Wala.

[Speaker 1]

Ay, paano. Ano pong ginagawa ng local government dito para ma-sustain nila yung ganito, yung woodcarving? Wala po pa silang ginagawa ng mga programa.

[Speaker 2]

Parang iba naman ang pamunuan dito. Hindi ka tulad sa ibang bayan.

[Speaker 1]

Hindi na nakasupporta sa inyo. Wala.

[Speaker 2]

Alaman ninyo, ma'am, noong pandemic noon, una, yung mayor namin dito, natalo

na nga at nagalit na kami lahat ng mamamayan. Pinalitan namin. Hindi pinamimigay yung dapat ay para sa akin.

[Speaker 1]

Bawal lumabas yung tao. Opo, yung mga ayuda.

[Speaker 2]

Oo, noon dyan. Tinambak dyan.

[Speaker 1]

Ano?

[Speaker 2]

Pabigay siya. Pinipili. Pibigay lang para sa lahat yun.

Napakarami na nabulok na lamang yung iba. Oo, meron ba namang ama ng bayan na ganyan? Uy, mga mamamayan, kakali kayo, karami.

Hanay kayo. Alam na wala namang pagbutuhanan.

[Speaker 1]

Pero po yung ngayong mayor nyo, ano po?

[Speaker 2]

Ay, okay naman.

[Speaker 1]

Wala po siyang bagong mga programa para sa inyo.

[Speaker 2]

Meron, magaganda.

[Speaker 1]

Merong housing yan. E kayo po, yung po sa pag-uukit lang po, meron kayang mga programa?

[Speaker 2]

Meron din yan.

[Speaker 1]

Meron din po si Mayor.

[Speaker 2]
Kasama sa ano nyo.

[Speaker 1]
So. Tanong po tayo sa mga bagong teknolohiya. Ano po kaya yung mga makabagong teknik o pamamaraan nyo or materyales na ginagamit nyo bilang tugun sa makabagong kondisyon ng klima?

Sa nagbabagong kondisyon. Meron po ba kayong specific na ginagamit? Kapag po sobrang init ng panahon, may ginagamit po ba kayong mga materyales?

O wala naman po?

[Speaker 2]
Wala.

[Speaker 1]
Wala, wala naman po.

[Speaker 2]
Basta sobrang init po tadya. May dalang upuan sa ilalim ng malaking puno.

[Speaker 1]
So wala po mga makabagong teknik or ano. Meron po ba kayong mga bagong likhang disenyo, produkto, bunga ng pagbabago ng inyong kapaligiran or dati po, ano po yung specific na ginagawa nyo po talaga before? O dito na po agad kayo?

[Speaker 2]
Yan talaga. Yan talaga lang.

[Speaker 1]
Saan po dinadala yan? Saan po dinadala yang inyong kabayo? Export yan.

Ah, ina-export.

[Speaker 2]
Tulad nito.

[Speaker 1]
Pagdating po sa kabayo...

[Speaker 2]
Meron sa sa Baguio.

[Speaker 1]
Magpapagawa ng kabayo, kayo po talaga?

[Speaker 2]
Sa kapatid ko dito.

[Speaker 1]
Ah, so ang export?

[Speaker 2]
Dalawa kami dyan eh.

[Speaker 1]
Kabayo. So saan po gawa yung inyong kabayo na yan? Iba-iba pong kahoy?

[Speaker 2]
Santol na nga yan.

[Speaker 1]
Santol na.

[Speaker 2]
Ubos na yung mga tatamim sa santol dito sa Paiti (Paete).

[Speaker 1]
Ano na pala ito? Ina-export na pala?

[Speaker 2]
Ano po? Hindi na sakay sa barko.

[Speaker 1]
Yung mga gamit nyo po dyan, gamit nyo na po? Or... Pinoprovide din nung inyong mga kabayo?

[Speaker 2]
Ano yung mayare? Kasi kami ganito lang. Kukunin na nila sila ng bahala, mga kinis, barnes (varnish).

[Speaker 1]
Yung pong mga bagong, mga resin-resin na gano'n, hindi po kayo na-adapt nun?

[Speaker 2]
Hindi. Ang tapang kasi ng amoy noon.
Masakit sa baga, masakit sa dibdib.

[Speaker 1]
Kasi parang sabi po kasi, doon sa ano,
pagka minsan, yung maliliit na imahe...

[Speaker 2]
O, ginaganon, magaganda.

[Speaker 1]
O, kasi lalo na kapag marami ang request.

[Speaker 2]
Ano po?

[Speaker 1]
Eh, kayo po talaga, ukit lang.

[Speaker 2]
Puro kahoy.

[Speaker 1]
So, kapag kaya...

[Speaker 1]
So, mayroon ba kayong bagong design?
Malapit na po tayo sa... Ano na po tayo?

Community. Kasi, paano nyo po kaya
mapapanatili? Bilang kayo po ay,
kumbaga, nagsimula sa kultura ng...

Nagpayaman sa kultura ng woodcarving
dito. Paano nyo po mapapanatili yung
inyong pagkakakilanlan? Kahit na medyo
nagbabago na yung panahon.

[Speaker 2]
Nagbabago na nga. Yung pati nga lakas,
yung parang pati mata, malabo.

[Speaker 1]
So, kayo po. Kung kayo po ay, ano, gusto
nyo po bang ipamana pa ito sa inyong
mga anak, sa inyong mga apo.

[Speaker 2]

Ibig sabihin na po, gusto ko, kaso parang
walang hilig. Maski nga, apo namin,
walang hilig.

[Speaker 1]
Pero inyo po, alam mo ba, tinuturuan,
gano'n? Nahawak naman po, kahit
papaano. Pero hindi rin talaga.

[Speaker 2]
Wala din.

[Speaker 1]
Ano po ngayon na mga hanap buhay ng
inyong mga anak?

[Speaker 2]
Ah, yung anak po, nandyan sa... MDR,
MDRRM mo dyan.

[Speaker 1]
Ah, sa local government po?

[Speaker 2]
Local.

[Speaker 1]
MDRRM?

[Speaker 2]
Rescue.

[Speaker 1]
Ano po kaya yung inyong rekomendasyon
sa inyong local government para po
mapatatag pa yung industriya nyo. Kasi
kung kayo po ibigay ng pagkakataong
makausap si mayor, para po masustain
yung... Mabait yung mayor namin ngayon
eh.

Pag po wala nang nagukit, baka po
malipat na ang woodcarving capital sa
ibang bayan. Sa ibang bayan.

[Speaker 2]
Oo nga.

[Speaker 1]
Ano po kaya kayo po...

[Speaker 2]
E kasama naman yung mayor sa aniya.
Hindi nila alisin niya.

[Speaker 1]
Papabaya naman.

[Speaker 2]
Lagi nga nila inuuna yung... Ito huwag
uhulihin kasi bawal niyang kahit. Bigyan
ng permit yung Pati kasi diyan nabubuhay
ang mamamayan sa ukit.

[Speaker 1]
Bigyan ng permit na...

[Speaker 2]
Bigyan naman. Sige, dalhin niya. Sa Paiti
pala yan, kay mayor pala yan.

Mayor agad na nang... nakikiusap.

[Speaker 1]
Ah, nabigyan ng permit.

[Speaker 2]
Pagkatulad lang namin, kukunin yun eh.

[Speaker 1]
Sino pong nakikipagusap?

[Speaker 2]
Si mayor.

[Speaker 1]
Si mayor.

[Speaker 2]
Bigyan niyo ng ano yan. Doon na umaasa
mga tao.

[Speaker 1]
Kaya, kasi kapag walang kakoy, wala nang
uuukitin.

[Speaker 2]
Wala nang uuukitin sa iba na. Katulad na,
napupunta na nga sa resin na dati. Wala
pa yan.

Taka.

[Speaker 1]
Ano nga ang taka?

[Speaker 2]
Yung paper.

[Speaker 1]
Ah, paper machine nga pala. Yung iba
alternative na kasi wala nang kakoy. So,
ayan lang po.

[Speaker 2]
Minsan nagkabagyo dito ng ano. Pati yung
mga kawayan dyan sa bundok natumba
yung lakas ng hangin. May ulan.

Ay, bagyo talaga.

[Speaker 1]
Yung pumpadar na yan, ay ano na po yan.
Bundok na ang kabila.

[Speaker 2]
May kalsada po. Bakod lang yan dyan sa
kabila.

[Speaker 1]
Pero malapit na po kayo sa bundok.

[Speaker 2]
O, ayan. May kalsada dyan papuntang
bayan.

[Speaker 1]
Yun niya, Sierra Madre.

[Speaker 2]
Sierra Madre na yan.

[Speaker 1]
Ang haba.

[Speaker 2]
Hanggang Quezon yan. Doon.

[Speaker 1]
Hanggang Aurora na po.

[Speaker 2]
Ano?

[Speaker 1]
Paikot to eh.

[Speaker 2]
Ang hangganan niyan, dagat na doon sa
Quezon na.

[Speaker 1]
Pulilio. Pulilio Island. Di ba po lagi ang
infanta ibaguhin?

[Speaker 2]
O, siya nga. Nasa ibabaw.

[Speaker 1]
Na-apectahan po. Nadadaan din po
kayo dito?

[Speaker 2]
Nadadaan dito. Galing sa kanila.

[Speaker 1]
Malakas pag sa infanta. Baguhin ang
infanta eh.

[Speaker 2]
Nasa ibabaw nila eh. Dagat na kasi.

[Speaker 1]
Sierra Madre.

[Speaker 2]
Tinakman kami ng bundok pag may
bagyuhan.

[Speaker 1]
Yun po mga taga Quezon, saan pong
bundok na nakuha ng mga kahoy kaya?

[Speaker 2]
Kung wala naman sila may mga kahoyan.

[Speaker 1]
Ah, private na nila. Tanim po nila?

[Speaker 2]
Lalo dyan sa Pulilio. Dami kamagong dyan.

[Speaker 1]
Tinatanim po nila?

[Speaker 2]
Tinatanim nila. Nasa matagal na panahon.

[Speaker 1]
Bago po makaputol ulit? Mga samputaon..

[Speaker 2]
Patay na yung nagtanim. Saka pa po yung
inakuha nila.

[Speaker 1]
Kaya nga. Gayo na nga. So, ayun lang po
marami na po matutunan sa iyo.

Transcribed by [TurboScribe.ai](https://www.turboscribe.ai)

APPENDIX E

Thematic Analysis of Data

This section contains the data analysis of the transcribed interviews with the participants. The coding scheme was generated to identify the major themes using thematic analysis.

Figure 26. Data analysis of the interview using thematic analysis.

Interviewee: Albert Noceja, MDRRM recording 2024-04-16 11-54-37
Transcribed by [TurboScribe.ai](#).

[Speaker 2]

Bale po ang tubig po niyan, pumasok po sa mga bahay po, sa mga shops?

[Speaker 1]

Hindi naman lahat ng bahay yan, kasi ang **bumaha samin** ay parte ng coastal area, malapit sa lake. Pero may mga bahay doon, yung formal settlers na nakatira sa highway, yun ang mga **nilubog ng kalahati ng bahay**, tapos nagtagal sila sa evacuation center.

May 703. Eh, makiprint nga ng record natin para sa **Typhoon Ondoy**. Makiprint ng lahat ng data natin sa Ondoy.

Salamat. Ano ba?

[Speaker 2]

Meron po kayong, hindi ko alam kung dito rin po. Tukol naman po sa batikuling.

[Speaker 1]

Batikuling, maraming propagation kasi naging...

[Speaker 2]

Dito po sa...

[Speaker 1]

Sa upland namin.

[Speaker 2]

Sa Paete po.

[Speaker 1]

Sa Paete mismo. Kasi ang Paete ay maliit lang itong kabayanan pero ano lang po, kilang, around 200 square meter lang itong bayan. Mostly ang lupa namin ay nasa upland.

[Speaker 2]

So yun po ay halimbawa po, parang itong na... Naging puno, kanino po siya? Pwede din po sa mga Paete?

[Speaker 1]

Oo, sa mga Paete. **Merong private, merong munisipal na nagme-maintenance ng mga puno.** Tapos, tawag dito...

Yung iba, yung private land nila, tinatiniman ng batikuling.

[Speaker 2]

Parang supply po para dito sa town lang po?

[Speaker 1]

Para dito sa bayan lang. **Yung ibang mga malalaking maguukit dito, may mga paggawaan talaga ng mga katulad ni... (Paloy Cagayat)** Dito sa tapat natin, ang malaking gawaan to na mga santo, na mga poon.

Yung kanina lupa sa upland, puro batik cooling ang tanim nila. Tapos, pag **nagtiriplanting kami**, palagi na ang inaan na namin sa batikuling at nara.

[Speaker 2]

Pero saan po nanggaling yung seeds?

[Speaker 1]

Yung seeds, kalimitan ay sa Department of Agriculture. Nakakapag-request kami. Tapos, yung iba naman...

Free lang din yata, malamang po. Kasi nga, pag nag-request, binibigyan kami. Tapos, dati, naka-MOU, **naka-MOA kami sa SLSU**, sa...

State U. Pagka nagpo-propagate sila, yun, nagso-supply din sila ng mga ganong klase.

[Speaker 2]

Yung po kayang... Kasi parang before po ay medyo madami pa po yung puno ng

batikuling. Yung po kayang trend po nung pag-decline po niya...

Kasi parang endangered...

[Speaker 1]

Halos na ubos dito. Kaya naman ngayon... Siguro last 5 to 10 years na magsimula ulit na mag-propagate ng batikuling dito sa bayan ng Paete.

Kasi nga, yung aming mga mag-ukit, wala na mga ukit na kahoy. Kaya kung ano-ano na lang na kahoy, minsan santol, lansones. Pagdil lansones na dami, inuukit na rin nila.

Tapos, yung iba naman dahil wala na halos na inuukit na kahoy, nag-transform naman sa ibang bagay kung mapapabalitan niyo ang Paete. Kahit ano inuukit na ngayon. Styro, chocolate, butter, prutas, yelo.

Oo yan, inuukit na rin. Yung mga dating mag-uukit dito, nagtitrabaho na nila mostly nasa abroad. Nag-uukit pa rin, kaso nga lang, iba na yung medium na inuukit nila.

Sa ibang bayan, sa ibang bansa. Oo, yung iba. Kung dito man, yung iba, dumayo na ng pampang, bataan.

Dahil doon, maraming kahoy yan.

[Speaker 2]

Yung kung sa dito po, kaya rin, sa batikuling kanino, kaya pwede nung matanong?

[Speaker 1]

Kay MPDC. MPDC? Hindi, kay MPDC.

Oo, pwede rin kay MPDC kasi siya rin yung aming agriculturist. Sa planning po, ano? Dalawa kasi yung hawak planning at saka yung agriculture.

Yung sa typhoon Ondoy, ayun, yun yung may share ko. Halos kalahating taon na po.

[Speaker 2]

Bukod po sa typhoon Ondoy, ano ba po yung pinakamalalang mga disaster? Earthquake, meron ba?

[Speaker 1]

Wala kasi. Ayun, earthquake, natatandaan ko yun na talagang, ano, hindi naman kami masyado earthquake, pero... Oo, ano lang, ang number one hazard namin, top two high risk hazard namin ay flood at saka landslide.

Number one yung flood, tapos number two yung landslide.

[Speaker 2]

Ang flood ba dahil po sa Manila Bay este laguna lake?

[Speaker 1]

Laguna Lake.

[Speaker 2]

Laguna Lake.

[Speaker 1]

Dahil sa Laguna Lake. Pagka-continuous yung, ano, yung pag-ulan, mapupunoy yung lake. Tapos pag nag-release ang caliraya, nag-release ang rizal ng tubig, pataas sa amin.

Oo, so yun yung cause ng flood. Tapos pagka-continuous din yung pag-ulan, lumalambot yung lupa. Erosyon. Landslide

Oo, nag-erosyon dito sa parte namin. Pero hindi naman yung sabihin mo na talagang grabe. Siguro, kaya lang naman.

Kaya naman ng ano, yung, ito, katulad dito sa parte Quinale, may landslide prone area kami dyan. Pag bumaha, sa kalasada lang sa highway, tapos nalilinis din naman

agad. Tapos wala naman kami yung sabihin mong nagiging casualty na natatabunan na bahay, natatabunan.

Wala naman.

[Speaker 2]
Flood at saka erosyon. So bukod dito sa typhoon, may instance ba po ba na tumaas ang tubig Laguna Lake?

[Speaker 1]
Oo. Kasi, sa totoo lang, yung aming Wawa Park. Okay, kumapapasyal kayo dyan.

Kalahating taon, lubog yun. Kalahating taon, nakalutang.

[Speaker 4]
Wawa Park.

[Speaker 1]
Oo, by January, yan, nag-subside na yan. Pero, asahamin na June to December, nakalubog yan. O kaya, July to December, nakalubog yan.

Hindi mo malalaruhan. Pero, by January, katulad ngayon, talaga naman magandang...

[Speaker 5]
Kasi, mainit.

[Speaker 1]
Mainit, oo. Pag-summer, yan, nakalutang yun. Mga pinta, may palaruan, may mga basketball court.

[Speaker 2]
Parang ito po yung parke. Parang parke dito. Kasama dito.

Tapos katabi dagat. Meron siya. May katabing dagat, kaya...

[Speaker 1]
Ano kami? Ang bahay ng Paite, in between ng Laguna Lake at saka nitong

Sierra Madre. Kaya, prone kami sa flood, prone kami sa landslide.

Kung makikita mo sa mapa natin.

[Speaker 2]
Ito yung park. Dito, may mga...

[Speaker 1]
Dito, may...

[Speaker 2]
Tapos, may bankado.

[Speaker 1]
Ito.

[Speaker 2]
Ah, may bankado. Oo, may bankado.

[Speaker 1]
Ito, ito. Kumakikita mo... Yan, parang...

[Speaker 3]
Ito yung Laguna Lake. Laguna de Bay. Ito yung Sierra Madre.

Ganyan lang. Around 200 plus square meter lang yung pahaba ng population.

[Speaker 2]
Ito na po ay una at dulo na...

[Speaker 1]
Oo, ito yung kalayaan. Within 10 minutes, kaya mo nang libutin ang bahay ng Paite. Ang population, 27,000 plus.

Ang ka-flat namin, 3,000 plus square meter. Pwede po mo... Lyon lang.

[Speaker 2]
Thank you po. Pag-iisipan ko paano akong gagawa ng mapa.

[Speaker 1]
Yan. Brief history na lang din.

[Speaker 2]
A, sige po.

[Speaker 1]
Ang bayan ng Paite ay may siyam na barangay. Siyam na barangay. Yung iba't ibang kulay nyan, ayan yun.

Barangay Uno ay yung kulay pink. Dito sa... Anong site po?

Sabihin natin, ganito tayo eh. Ito yung Laguna Lake.

[Speaker 3]
Ito yung Sierra Madre. North, South, East, West. Southern part, yung kalahati ng barangay.

Uno, dos, tres, cuatro, cinco. Tapos, another part, yung... One, two, three, four, five, six, seven, eight, nine.

Meron kaming dalawang barangay dito na has a population of 5,500. Itong yellow, at sya itong... Ano yung bahulay nila?

Bahulay nila? Hindi, orange. Oo, parang gano'n.

Ayan, ito lang yan. Pinaka maliit ito.

[Speaker 2]
Ah, yung po ay nasa barangay?

[Speaker 1]
Nasa barangay 4. Ito yung location natin. Ito yung pinaka biggest population, barangay 4.

Ayan, narito tayo sa... Ito yung location natin.

[Speaker 2]
Nasa unahan lang pala tayo. Dato pa pala talaga yung...

[Speaker 1]
Yung kabayanan namin. Pero sabihin mo, ten minutes kaya mo na lalakar at libutin itong bayan.

[Speaker 2]

Hindi, akin na ito. May record na. Sa unong kilaligtas.

Pagdating naman po sa... Sa pagpuputol na puno ngayon, Totally bawal na.

[Speaker 1]
Pero kung... Kung kailangang putulin dahil delikado, na magka cause ng disaster, maaaring may babagsakan. Ina-allow.

[Speaker 2]
Pero po yung pag dun sa mga woodcarvers natin?

[Speaker 1]
Ah, yung kahoy nila nanggagaling na rin lang sa ibang bayan. Sa ngayon. Kasi wala na talagang mga-wood yan sa amin sa taas.

Wood na pwedeng maging medium ng ukit. Kaya nga sabihin ko dati ng mga nakaraang. Ultimo, manga, lanzones.

[Speaker 2]
Pero before po, kung wala po yung total, nakakaputol po.

[Speaker 1]
Nakakaputol talaga sila.

[Speaker 2]
Pero medyo tedious daw po yung documentation. Kaya po hindi sila maka-apply. Naramdang strict talaga.

Diyan po sa mga documentation namin, kanino naman pwede matanong? Pagkuha po ng permit.

[Speaker 1]
Sa DA din. Lagi. Lagi na sa DA din.

Tama-tama, yung aming MENRO at yung aming DA MPDC nasa isang office lang sila. Sa munisipal. Pupunta rin kayo doon?

Alam, alam. Pulas 12 naman. Mga 1 o'clock na kayo nakapunta.

[Speaker 2]
Kayo ko ba naka-break?

[Speaker 1]
Hindi naman. Nakakain na ba kayo?

[Speaker 2]
Opo, opo.

[Speaker 1]
Meron tayo dyang ano.

[Speaker 2]
Nung COVID-19 naman po, ano naman pong nangyari dito sa...

[Speaker 1]
Dito, opo, very strict kami. Dahil maliit lang yung bahay namin. **Totally lockdown.**

Pagkasabi namin totally lockdown, lockdown. Walang makakapasok, walang makakalabas.

[Speaker 2]
Yung pong sa industry po nila?

[Speaker 1]
Industry? **Shutdown ang industry namin.** Lahat pahingaan.

[Speaker 2]
Paano po yung kanilang income?

[Speaker 1]
Yung kanilang income... Depende sa kabuhayan ng mga katrabaho noon. Pero hanggat maaari.

Hanggat kaya ng munisipal o ng **mga mahihingan namin, sinusuplayan namin.**

[Speaker 5]
Ayudan lang po.

[Speaker 1]
Ayudan. Tapos meron kami mga generous ng mga kababayan na nasa abroad. Papadala sila.

Tapos minamanage namin kung paano namin masaseparate. Tapos, minaximize namin yung aming mga resources hanggat may mahihingan kami. Manghihinga kami.

Katulad sa custom noong nagbigay sila ng isda.

[Speaker 2]
Nagpibigay sa bahay.

[Speaker 1]
Yan. Hanggat maaari. Yung kami na nakakalabas.

Kami, tumarabaho na tumarabaho. Kung paano kami makapag...

[Speaker 2]
Frontliners, eh.

[Speaker 1]
Paano kami makapag-provide na ibibigay sa kanila. Lalo-lalo na yung mga hindi nakatrabaho.

[Speaker 2]
Oo. Di yung mga registered woodcarving industry sa... ang mga...

ang mga...

[Speaker 1]
Oo. Sa... Sa ano naman yan?

Sa... Sa business permit. Yung mga naka-registro namin.

Kung ilan sila. Doon din lang sa munisipyon. Sa second floor.

Kung ilan yung registered namin na woodcarving. Dito... ng locals.

Farming. Kaso, sabi ko nga sa'yo, **bibihira yung farming. Yung iba...**

paper mache. Dito rin sa'min yung paper mache. Tapos ano pa...

yung ibang trabaho dito. Farming. Paper mache.

Number one dito sa'min ngayon ay... yung pagiging OFW. Seafarer.

Yung... seafarer. OFW.

Kung hindi nasa barko. Nasa... mga hotel.

Ay.

[Speaker 4]
Kasi... wala po... wala pong record naman.

So, kasi tayo po nang 2019. 2019.

[Speaker 1]
Wala. Makakakuha ka niyan ay sa MSWD naman. O, kasi...

itong opisina namin nag-restart kami 2017 naman. 2017 December. Nung...

ano-ano namin.

[Speaker 2]
Sa... tingin nyo po yung... woodcarving industry po dito sa...

inyo po. Masusustain pa rin po sa mahamang panahon. Ngayon, naubusan po tayo na.

[Speaker 1]
Sa totoo lang ay ngayon ay... kumunti. Kasi kumunti yung supply, yung demand.

Ngayon, kung hindi gagawa ng paraan na aasa lang sa ibang bayan, baka mawala. Kaya ang ginagawa natin ngayon is... makapag...

makapag... para makasustain, eh, yun, tree planting ng batikuling.

[Speaker 2]
Yung pong lupa po doon ay government po?

[Speaker 1]
Ah, yun nga, sabi ko nga kanina. Yung mga may private land.

[Speaker 2]
Ah, meron.

[Speaker 1]
Katulad din na itong sa tapat natin.

[Speaker 2]
Nagtatanim.

[Speaker 1]
Nagtatanim sila ng mga batikuling sa kanilang private land. Tapos, ang municipal naman natin, pagka... ano, nakikipag-agreement doon sa iba na, oh, tatanim man natin, alagahan natin.

[Speaker 2]
Parang na... pahiram lang po ng mga lupa at tayo. Tapos, government lang po.

[Speaker 1]
Ah, government ng mga gaano. Meron tayong ano dyan, ah, mga bantay kalikasan. Sila nag-maintain.

Sila rin nagbabantay dyan. Parang doon sa mga illegal logger, mga naghuling.

[Speaker 2]
Kayo po, naroon rin po kayo maglilok?

[Speaker 1]
Ako? Oo. Pero hindi ako, ano, hindi ako...

magaling ng ruling. Natuto lang dyan.

[Speaker 2]
Nakakahawak din po.

[Speaker 1]
Kasi dito sa amin, ano, ah, nung panahon bata pa kami, pag elementary, kaya ganyan ang project sa school. Tuturuan na kayo.

[Speaker 2]

May subject po ba yan?

[Speaker 1]

Ah, practical... Ah, sa amin, ah, sa high school, practical arts, elementary, workshop. Sa workshop namin, ayang ginagawa namin.

Pag hindi kami gumagawa, pag hindi kami nagukit, gagawa kami ng mga carpentry, bangkito, upuan. Kaya, nung time na yan, talaga, at saka makikita mo naman nung time namin, marami pang magukit at saka yung mga magulang namin, mga tito, tita, ganyan ang kabuhayan, eh, uobligahin ka, nakita. Nakita mo sa bahay.

Pero ngayon, sabi ko nga, bibihira na. Umunti na.

[Speaker 2]

Pati po mga youth ngayon, parang, hindi na po masyado mainteresado sa talaga yung cultural, mga kapatid.

[Speaker 1]

Ngayon, iilan na lang. Kasi nga, sa school, pagka yung, sabi ko nga, dati ganyan ang project namin. Ngayon, ah, hindi na gasino.

[Speaker 2]

Inalis na po ba yun sa school?

[Speaker 1]

Hindi naman. Pinalitan lang nila na medium ginawang sabon na lang.

[Speaker 2]

Oh.

[Speaker 1]

Ah, yung mga batang ngayon, sabun na lang inuukit. Hindi na kagaya namin talaga dati, talaga kahoy.

[Speaker 2]

saka humahawak po kayo naman.

[Speaker 1]

O, tapos, pagdating mo sa bahay, ah, para magkabaon ka kinabukasan, kailangan mong, ah, magukit kahit paano. Oo. Kaya matututo ka talaga.

Dahil, yun ang babaunin mo pangabukasan. Pag hindi ka nalang gumawa, walang baon.

[Speaker 2]

So, less na po talaga yung mga interisado.

[Speaker 1]

Kaya naman ano eh, ah, ang munisipal natin tinatrain na, yung, meron kami nga dito eh, yung culinary training center na libreng nagtuturo sa mga bata na magukit. Ganyan.

[Speaker 2]

Free, free training mo.

[Speaker 1]

Oo.

[Speaker 2]

Ano po, every year.

[Speaker 1]

Every year, oo. Tapos, bukod pa dyan, yung initiative ng mga matatandang magukit na rito na may mga paukitan, ah, pwede silang, ano, puntahan ng mga bata, ano, tuturuan sila, ganyan. So, meron pa yung Para hindi mamatay yung, ano, yung, free demo sa mga shops.

Oo. Oo. Para hindi mamatay yung kultura, yung pinanggalingan na paite talaga.

[Speaker 2]

Ano po, ah, dito po pala, ah, yung sobrang init po. Kasi, before po, ganto na rin po ba kainit yun.

[Speaker 1]

Hindi, mas mainit ngayon. Kahit naman saan, siguro. Kasi, una, una, nabawasan na yung ating mga puno.

Dito, ganoon din sa amin, ramdam namin. Tapos, ah, kumapal na yung population. Ah.

Dumami ng structure ng mga bahay. Hindi ka tulad dati, na, walang matataas na bahay. Pag may second floor ka dati, okay na.

Ngayon, makikita ko, may third floor, may fourth floor. Kaya, yun, yun yung mga nakaka, ano rin.

[Speaker 2]
Nakaka-experience din po kayo ng forest fire?

[Speaker 1]
Forest fire, ah, dito, hindi naman forest fire na malaki. Ah, nakaka-experience kayo. Siguro, ah, sa isang taon po kayo?

Sa isang taon, hindi naman palagi. Pero mayroong taon kami na, anong taon ba yan? 2018 o 19?

Ah, hindi naman malakihan dahil, kinaya pa rin ng mga mamamayan eh. Ah, ng Bureau of Fire namin, kami.

[Speaker 2]
Ah, parang naagapan naman?

[Speaker 1]
Naagapan naman, oo. Pero, siguro, hindi naman, grabe siguro.

[Speaker 2]
May data po kayo? O, kayo picture?

[Speaker 1]
Sa?

[Speaker 2]
Yung po forest fire, may data po kayo Hindi ko maalala kung meron kami eh.

[Speaker 1]
Pero meron naman, siguro, Bureau of Fire. Hindi, hindi naman. O, natatandaan ko

yan, bago pala kami nag-uumpisan ulit dito sa DRRM.

[Speaker 2]
So, wala namang na-affect?

[Speaker 1]
Wala namang, sa taas lang. O, ano lang yan, mga kawayanan, kasi, tapos, yun, mga natuyo na kawayan, ano.

[Speaker 2]
Bali po, yung pinaka-plan po ng paete, part na po ng Sierra Madre?

[Speaker 5]
O, part na Sierra Madre.

[Speaker 2]
Kasi nga, yun lang po, yun lang po, Sir Albert. Okay na? Yun lang po, opo.

[Speaker 1]
Ano pa? Data ng population, gusto mo?

[Speaker 2]
Pwede po, data ng population. Habi dyan, OBF. Yung po mga forest conservation sa, sa ano na rin po, ito, sa DA?

O, ito yung updated namin.

[Speaker 1]
2024. Ito sa mga barangay. Diba sabi ko naman siya, meron kami population.

[Speaker 2]
500 lang.

[Speaker 1]
Itong, bangko siya, yung pinakamalit, 474 lang. Ito, 500.

Transcribed by [TurboScribe.ai](#).

Themes

Codes

Knowledge, Perceptions, and Skills of Paete wood carvers related to climate-change

- Bumaha samin
- Nilubog ng kalahati ng bahay
- Typhoon ondoy
- Halos kalahating taon na po.
- High risk hazard namin ay flood at saka landslide
- Dahil sa Laguna Lake. Pagka-continuous yung, ano, yung pag-ulan, mapupunoy yung lake.
- Yung pag-ulan, lumalambot yung lupa. Erosyon. Landslide
- Katulad dito sa parte Quinale, may landslide prone area kami dyan. Pag bumaha, sa kalasada lang sa highway, tapos nalilinis din naman
- Oo. Kasi, sa totoo lang, yung aming Wawa Park. Kalahating taon, lubog yun. Kalahating taon, nakalutang
- Mainit, oo. Pag-summer, yan, nakalutang yun
- Kaya, prone kami sa flood, prone kami sa landslide
- Sa pagpuputol na puno ngayon, Totally bawal na.
- Oo. Pero hindi ako, ano, hindi ako...
- Magaling ng ruling. Natuto lang dyan
- Nung panahon bata pa kami, pag elementary, kaya ganyan ang project sa school. Tuturuan na kayo.
- Sa high school, practical arts, elementary, workshop.
- Pag hindi kami nagukit, gagawa kami ng mga carpentry, bangkito, upuan
- Mas mainit ngayon
- Kumapal na yung population
- Dumami ng structure ng mga bahay
- Makikita ko, may third floor, may fourth floor.
- Forest fire, ah, dito, hindi naman forest fire na Malaki. Pero mayroong taon kami na, anong taon ba yan? 2018 o 19?
- Ano lang yan, mga kawayanan, kasi, tapos, yun, mga natuyo na kawayan, ano.

Influence of climate change on livelihoods, economic sustainability, market demand for Paete wood carvings

- Halos na ubos dito
- Yung aming mga mag-ukit, wala na mga ukit na kahoy.
- Dahil wala na halos na inuukit na kahoy
- Yung mga dating mag-uukit dito, nagtitrabaho na nila mostly nasa abroad.
- Yung iba, dumayo na ng pampangang, bataan.
- Yung kahoy nila nanggagaling na rin lang sa ibang bayan
- Wala na talagang mga-wood yan sa amin sa taas.
- Totally lockdown. Pagkasabi namin totally lockdown, lockdown. Walang makakapasok, walang makakalabas.
- Shutdown ang industry namin
- Yung kanilang income... Depende sa kabuhayan ng mga katrabaho noon
- Bibihira yung farming. Yung iba...
- Paper mache. Dito rin sa'min yung paper mache.
- Number one dito sa'min ngayon ay... Yung pagiging OFW. Seafarer.
- Kung hindi nasa barko. Nasa... Mga hotel.
- Pero ngayon, sabi ko nga, bibihira na. Umunti na.

Innovative techniques, materials, and artistic processes in response to changing weather and climatic conditions

- Minsan santol, lansones. Pagdil lansones na dami, inuukit na rin nila.
- Inuukit na ngayon. Styro, chocolate, butter, prutas, yelo.
- Pinalitan lang nila na medium ginawang sabon na lang.
- Tinatrain na, yung, meron kami nga dito eh, yung culinary training center na libreng nagtuturo sa mga bata na magukit.
- Every year, oo. Tapos, bukod pa dyan, yung initiative ng mga matatandang magukit na rito na may mga paukitan, ah, pwede silang, ano, puntahan ng mga bata, ano, tuturuan sila, ganyan.

The resilience of the Paete wood carving community in the face of climate-related challenges, while preserving their cultural identity and heritage

- Batikuling, maraming propagation Sa upland namin
- Merong private, merong munisipal na nagme-maintenance ng mga puno.
- Yung iba, yung private land nila, tinatiniman ng batikuling
- Yung ibang mga malalaking maguukit dito, may mga paggawaan talaga ng mga katulad ni... (Paloy Cagayat)
- Nagtiri-planting kami,
- Yung seeds, kalimitan ay sa Department of Agriculture
- Naka-MOA kami sa SLSU State U. Pagka nagpo-propagate sila, yun, nagso-supply din sila ng mga ganong klase.
- Sa totoo lang ay ngayon ay... Kumunti. Kasi kumunti yung supply, yung demand.
- Tree planting ng batikuling.
- . Meron tayong ano dyan, ah, mga bantay kalikasan. Sila nag-maintain.

APPENDIX F

Local Climate Change Action Plan and Contingency Plan

This section includes the cover page photo of the municipal document: Local Climate Change Action Plan (LCCAP) 2021-2026 and Contingency Plan for Flood and Landslide of Paete, Laguna.

Figure 27. Cover page of LCCAP and Contingency Plan of Paete, Laguna.

Note: The full document copy was obtained from the MENRO and MDRRM Office of Paete Laguna. These documents were used as source of secondary information.

APPENDIX G

Paete Artisans

This section features photographs of Paete artisans showcasing their expertise.

Figure 28. Paete artisans with their expertise.

Note: Edmund Lanuza, with three decades of experience, is celebrated for his meticulously crafted door designs featured in various churches across the Philippines. One of his remarkable works is carving of one of the versions of the Philippine President's seal (*Sagisag ng Pangulo ng Pilipinas*).

Note: Jose Maralita is renowned for his expertise in carving the symbolic carabao image for the Boy Scout of the Philippines. He often crafts these carabaos using santol wood.

Note: Zaldy Coronel is renowned for his expertise in crafting horse images in various sizes. He accepts bulk orders for these items, which are often exported by the customer.

APPENDIX H

Tourist Arrivals Summary

This section provides the summary of the tourist arrivals from year 2006 up to first quarter of 2024 in Paete, Laguna.

Figure 29. Tourists arrival in Paete, Laguna.

Republic of the Philippines
Province of Laguna
Municipality of Paete

MUNICIPAL TOURISM OFFICE
Tel No. (049) 501-7730 Fax No. (049) 557-0001

Month	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026
January	922	39	876	1,465	2,361		
February	1,533	61	2,085	1,758	2,275		
March	1,756	42	2,717	10,015	16,880		
April	COVID	148	874	6,790			
May	COVID	654	898	1,173			
June	COVID	277	416	1,121			
July	COVID	48	1,242	1,416			
August	COVID	12	2,781	2,088			
September	COVID	2	2,020	1,736			
October	14	1098	1,945	1,415			
November	11	1309	2,444	1,834			
December	1	524	1,578	2,036			
TOTAL	4,237	4,214	19,876	32,847			

Month	2027	2028	2029	2030	2031	2032	2033
January							
February							
March							
April							
May							
June							
July							
August							
September							
October							
November							
December							
TOTAL							

Note: The summary indicates that before the COVID-19 pandemic, there was a substantial influx of tourists arriving in the town of Paete, Laguna. After the pandemic, tourist arrivals were returned to normalcy last year.